

Middle East University
Faculty of Business Administration

FINANCING LEBANESE PUBLIC DEBT WITH
REMITTANCE-BACKED SECURITIES

A Thesis

Presented in Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirements for the Degree
Master of Business Administration

by

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May 2017

THESIS ABSTRACT

Master of Business Administration

Middle East University

Faculty of Business Administration

Title: FINANCING LEBANESE PUBLIC DEBT WITH REMITANCE-BACKED SECURITIES

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Date completed: April, 2017

Having a history of instability, devastating wars, political turbulence and as a result high, constantly growing, sometimes even unmanageable public debt Lebanon at the same time has one of the world's highest levels of expatriate's remittance inflows. Nevertheless, the Lebanese authorities do not have a clear vision of how to structure such a substantial amount of remittances for the common good of the country.

This paper attempts to provide the link among growing public debt, remittances and one of the recent financial innovation – securitization. The research uses post-positivism paradigm by utilizing mainly the quantitative methodology relying on a statistical analysis which uses several tools such as times series, simple, and multiple regression models, and inferential statistics in order to check the causality relation among quantitative variables such as the net total debt, GDP, time, and remittances. In addition, the analytic narrative is used to read and analyze the

numerical data. Secondary quantitative data and case studies are also used and analyzed regarding the topic of public debt, remittances and securitization.

As a result, all of the stated hypotheses were tested positively implying that Lebanon, as one of the heavily indebted countries, has a need of restructuring its public debt and obtaining external financing. Also, Lebanon has an opportunity for acquiring inexpensive external financing using a stable and countercyclical remittances inflow. Thus, government authorities should consider remittances not only as source of Balance of Payment benefits, but also as means of affordable international borrowing while strengthening the link between expatriates and their home country, Lebanon.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ABL	Association of Banks in Lebanon
ABS	Asset-Backed Securities
BCC	Banking Control Commission
BdB	Banco do Brasil
BDL	Banque du Liban
BOP	Balance of Payment
FDI	Foreign Direct Investment
GCC	Gulf Council Countries
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
HTA	Home Town Associations
IMF	International Monetary Fund
ITRS	International Transactions Reporting System
LERC	Lebanese Emigrants Research Center
MOF	Ministry of Finance
NDU	Notre Dame University
ODA	Official Development Assistance
RBB	Remittance-Backed Bonds
RBS	Remittance-Backed Securities
SPV	Special Purpose Vehicle
UAE	United Arab Emirates
WB	World Bank

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

At the beginning, I would like to thank Heavenly Father, who inspired me to write this research always providing health, wisdom and motivation for the accomplishment of my studies.

I would like to express my gratitude and appreciation to Dr. Ghalia Hamami, the research advisor, who guided the research on its early stages. I sincerely thank Dr. Malcolm Russell who offered his guidance and helped me to accomplish my work bringing it to the highest possible standard. Also, my gratitude goes to the faculty and staff of the Middle East University for their support through my research.

I owe my appreciation to my parents, dear family members and Seventh-day Adventists friends who prayed for me, supported and encouraged me during the process of writing this research.

CHAPTER 1 INTRODUCTION

Background

When financial crisis of 2007 took place, global financial markets were affected to the extent that it took years for many world economies to recover. Moreover, some of the effects are still being felt. The so-called sub-prime crisis began when borrowers in the United States failed to pay their house loans (mortgages). The chain reaction affected many private investors, financial institutions and financial systems even of the wealthiest countries. The crisis led to the collapse of Lehman Brothers, the fiscal stimulus, and huge government efforts in bringing economies in to pre-crisis levels (The Economist, 2013). Lenders, greediness of investors, lack of regulations, a "saving glut" in Asia and, as the result, low interest rates contributed to the crisis. However, one of the most important reasons of the credit crunch was securitization and, as a result, asset-backed securities that were massively traded at the global financial markets.

Securitization was "the greatest financial innovation in the 20th century" because it allowed banks to off load the risks and created additional money (Anup, 2013). In order to diversify the risks of various loans, bankers would pull them into sellable securities.

Obviously, risky loans were not the best assets for securitization. But what are the good assets that can be used as underlying? They should be stable, countercyclical, and projected receivables that could be farther pooled, underwritten and sold as assets-backed securities (*Asset Securitization*, 1997).

Analyzing recent trends in global movement of capital, we believe that expatriates' remittances might be a good example of underlying assets. Remittances are cash flows that emigrants manage to send back to their home countries. According to the World Bank data, remittances "remain a key source of external resource flows for developing countries, far exceeding official development assistance and more stable than private debt and portfolio equity flows" (World Bank, 2016). Being a great source of foreign exchange, they are one of the major components of balance of payment.

Statement of the Problem

Being one of the most indebted countries in the world, Lebanon does not have a choice but to keep borrowing money to pay its dues. However, the interest over the debt may vary regarding the way the funds are borrowed. Currently, Lebanese government borrows locally in Lebanese pounds and US Dollars. More than a half of the debt is held by the Lebanese commercial banks (57%) while the Central Bank of Lebanon buys back about 20%. Nearly 13% of the public debt is held by other public and private local institutions; while only less than 10% is held by non-residents (This Public Debt, 2014). The portfolio of public debt consists of government bonds, bills and loans. In 2013, nearly 40% of total debt was borrowed in USD, while around 60% was borrowed in LBP. The total weighted average interest rate was 6.4% (Ministry of finance, 2014). Thus, Lebanon is obliged to keep financing its debt at a high interest rate or to look for alternative ways. In addition, Lebanon has a low sovereign credit rating. Standard & Poor's Rating Services, assigned to Lebanon B-/B rating with a negative outlook (Cullinan & Jelencovic, 2015). The low rating deters Lebanon from borrowing internationally. If Lebanon decides to borrow from the international market, its treasury bills will be considered very risky (or junk), thus Lebanon will

have to compensate for the high risk with a high interest rate. This is not possible in the situation when the current level of the public debt of Lebanon represents huge burden to the whole economy.

This research attempts to provide an alternative way of debt financing through recent financial innovation - securitization backed by the most stable flow of expatriates' remittances.

Problem Statement

Thus, the problem statement will be: How to obtain international financing for a developing country with a low credit rating? And how to finance public debt at lower interest rate?

These questions will be answered through the following research questions.

Is there a need for Lebanon to get financing from international market?

Is there a way to get financing through remittance-backed securities?

How to borrow from international markets using remittances inflows to Lebanon?

What are the benefits to Lebanon from borrowing through remittance-backed securities?

Rationale and Objective of the Study

Presidential vacuum, political turmoil and increasing number of Syrian refugees' impact already unstable Lebanese economy. Severe public debt caused by chronic budget and current account deficits, high interest rate over internationally borrowed fund and large amount of domestic debt that forecasted to be a potential bottle neck are not promising a bright future for Lebanon. However, the high migration rate and the large amount of funds that are sent back to Lebanon on a

regular basis are a lifebuoy of the Lebanese economy. All of these facts contributed to the determination of the topic of this research.

How to link richly poured expatriates' inflows to Lebanon with the unsustainable public debt? In the simplest way, remittance inflows, while being constant and countercyclical, are one more affordable method of public debt financing. The major sources of capital inflows to Lebanon are FDI, bank deposits, and tourism and portfolio investments. However, they are all outperformed by remittances, which amount nearly US\$ 8 billion in 2014 (The World Bank, 2016). After Syria's eviction in 2005, close relations with GCC states led to an inflow of petrodollars and the outflow of Lebanese workers that sent their money back home. Since that time remittances inflows to Lebanon were firmly established (Henry & Springborg, 2010. pp. 296-300).

There are certain benefits of this research. Knowing the fact that remittances have been major contributors to the Lebanese GDP for several decades, we will take a look at the reasons why while analyzing recent trends of remittances inflows. In addition, we will observe best practices of countries that have been using remittances for development financing. Also, we will look at recent ways of budget deficit financing while comparing them to the goals of Ministry of Finance Debt Management Strategy of 2016. At the end of the research we will provide a solution of how Lebanon could leverage positive effect of remittances and partially finance its public debt.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of the presented research consists of a review of the Lebanese public debt, its major components, and related issues. It also includes an explanation of the impact of outflow migration and its benefits for Lebanon. The

research also describes the process of securitization and specifically its recent innovation, remittance-backed securities. Finally, the research analyzes an example of issuance of securities backed by remittances of Brazil and suggests this scheme to Lebanon as a possibility for external borrowing and public debt financing.

Field Characteristics, Problems and Limitations

The field is mostly limited to the Lebanese economy. However, international examples that are relevant to the study would be looked at. Data starting from the independence of Lebanon in 1943 has been collected and analyzed to be put in the most meaningful way. In Lebanon, several research-based have been made about importance of remittances inflows to Lebanon. However, none of them wrote about the use of remittances in debt financing or acquiring funds from international markets. The research attempts to combine international experiences with future-flow securitization with the rich inflow of remittances in Lebanon. However, we face several limitations. Since the research tries to apply best practices of foreign countries, there might be a problem finding a country with the same level of development as Lebanon. Also, due to current political turbulence in Lebanon, it may be problematic to obtain an authority's point of view about our topic.

Significance of the Study

This study is important due to several reasons. First, Lebanon currently faces the situation of an unsustainable upward trend of the public debt, with one of the highest debt-to-GDP ratio of nearly 140 percent. Local authorities state that financing such a high amount of the public debt locally would be challenging in near future (Audi Bank, 2015; Daou & Mikhael, 2015; Ministry of Finance, 2010; Ministry of Finance, 2014; Neaime, 2014). International authorities mention that local

accumulation of the Lebanese public debt endangers the development of the whole economy (Cullinan & Jelencovic, 2015; Shineller, 2014). At the same time, Lebanon constantly receives substantial funds from the Lebanese migrants abroad (nearly US\$ 7 billion a year). Those money inflows into Lebanon are stable and countercyclical even during turbulent times and remain underutilized by the Lebanese government (Abdih et al., 2009; Agunais & Newland, 2012; Cohen et al., 2012; Hourani, 2007; Ketkar & Ratha, 2001). This research attempts to look at remittances from several angles providing means for the affordable way of the external financing of the public debt.

Definitions

Major definitions of the presented work are the following.

Public debt. The debt that a government acquires in order to cover its excess spending.

Remittances. Money that migrants send back to their home country.

Securitization. The process on issuing and selling securities (internally and externally) value of which derives from (backed by) a pool of homogeneous assets.

Future-flow securities. Securities that are backed by an expected and carefully forecasted future flow of assets.

Remittance-backed securities. Securities that are backed by the predicted inflow of remittances.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

Countries usually do not rely only on their public finances to survive. They also rely on public debt and on emigrants' remittances. However, in heavily indebted countries, remittance-backed securities could be part of the solution. Therefore, when talking about such an issue, one should address public finances, the public debt, remittances, and securitization.

Public Finance

According to Adam Smith's "Wealth of Nations" (2007), the public finance is referred to as "the investment into the nature and principles of state expenditure and state revenue". Early researchers generally discussed public finance as revenue collection through taxes for the purpose of defense and administration. In his fifth book "Of the Revenue of the Sovereign or Commonwealth", Adam Smith describes the four major duties of a sovereign that require expense.

The first is the duty of defense, since the government is responsible to protect its country from the oppression of other societies. The second duty of a country is to protect its citizens from injustice from any other member of society, thus, the establishment of an administration of justice is required. The third duty is maintaining public institutions that "are necessary for facilitating commerce,"- mainly infrastructure and trading companies, and institutions "for the education of youth,"- such as colleges and universities including religious education. Finally, it is the duty of the country to bear the "expense of supporting the dignity of the sovereign" which

is an expense of maintaining royal status and splendor of a monarchy. Thus, those four duties are the major expenses of a sovereign.

Smith also describes the major contributor to the sovereign's revenues, taxes. In the "Part Third", he mentions various taxes that the government should collect, such as taxes upon rent, profits, revenues, employment, wages, capitalization and consumable commodities. Since most of the time, sovereign expenses surpass revenues, Smith talks about public debt as a way for acquiring additional funds, especially during the time of a war. In his chapter III "of Public Debts" Smith describes situation when a country faces a war and does not have means to finance expenses through additional taxes. Then a sovereign should borrow from wealthy "merchants and manufacturers" by issuing treasury bills, both interest bearing and non-interest bearing. Beginning in the 17th century, European countries increasingly borrowed money. Many of them became heavily indebted, particularly England and France (Smith, Edited 2007).

Nowadays, the functions of the modern government have widened to the extent that it has to perform new functions to support its citizens. Generally, the field of public finance is split into four major parts of study, such as *Public Debt*, *Public Revenue*, *Public Expenditure* and *Budgeting*.

Public Revenue, Expenses, and Budget

The government budget is prepared by the authorities on annual basis and is comprised of three main parts, which are the total revenues, the total expenses, and the public debt. Appendix I provides an example of the Fiscal Balance of Lebanon. Figure 1 summarizes this balance.

Figure 1. The fiscal balance of Lebanon.

Self-made figure based on the Government Budget, by Ministry of Finance, 2011, retrieved from www.finance.gov.lb

Section one of the balance includes the *total revenue* that the government receives, including both tax and non-tax revenue. Tax revenue (as the name implies) derives from tax, for example, tax on income, properties, goods and services, international trade, etc. Non-tax revenue includes income from public institutions and government properties, such as rent fees from Rafic Hariri International Airport, and administrative fees and charges. According to Smith, in cases when a sovereign is not able to borrow or save enough money, it should extend its system of taxation (Smith, Edited in 2007). Thus, in 2001 the Lebanese authorities enacted the Value Added Tax (VAT) Law in order to increase fiscal revenue.

According to the Investment Development Authority of Lebanon (IDAL), VAT is applied on imported goods and on goods and services carried out by a taxable person. Essential goods and services, together with goods of the agriculture, health, and education sectors of the economy, Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and financial services are tax exempted. VAT in Lebanon used to be 10%, but in March, 2017 the Lebanese Parliament approved the VAT increase from 10% to 11% (Lebanon Sales Tax Rate, 2017). However, VAT in Lebanon is still among the smallest in Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region compared, for example, to Morocco (20%) and to Jordan (16%) (VAT, 2001).

Finally, the last part of the revenue section is the *treasury receipts*. Those are mainly zero-coupon bonds that are stripped (principal and coupon payment are separated), collateralized by treasury, and sold at large discount.

The second section of the fiscal balance of Lebanon records the *total expenditures*. *Current expenditures* and *capital expenditures* are the major expenditures in this section. Current expenditures among others include *interest payment on debt* in domestic and foreign currencies together with *foreign debt principal repayment*. It also includes cost of personnel and other current expenses. Capital expenditures are comprised mostly by infrastructure expenses, equipment and maintenance. The last section of the budget balance records *public debt* in local and foreign currencies.

Finally, there are three possible outcomes of the government budget and they are related whether total revenues are greater than total expenditures or not. The Figure 2 illustrates those outcomes.

Figure 2. Budget outcome.

Self-made figure based on data by Banque Du Liban, 2013, retrieved from www.bdl.gov.lb

Unfortunately, and in most of the cases, governments face budget deficits, where state expenses exceed revenues. In this case, the government borrows additional funds to balance the budget. Simply speaking, government's spending

minus revenues equals to government's deficit, and the accumulated deficits become the national debt.

In some cases, the government may enjoy a *primary surplus*. It takes place when government's income is greater than its expenses. When a country has a debt that has been financed and has interest on it, then a government's expenses plus the interest may be greater than its revenues. This is called overall deficit (see Figure 3). Many countries face primary surplus while having overall deficit.

Figure 3. Overall deficit and primary surplus.

Self-made figure based on the knowledge of this chapter.

Here, it should be worth to understanding why a country has a budget / fiscal deficit. As a matter of fact, moderate spending on infrastructure or investments is considered healthy since they produce revenues or taxes in the future. In contrast, unsustainable expenses or low revenue collection are considered unhealthy. However, it is also important to know the structures of the government debt and the means through which a state may manages it. Consequently, the following paragraphs will mention the theoretical foundations of the public debt and of the debt sustainability analysis.

Public Debt

Public debt is a current issue nowadays. In order to understand it, the following writings will shed light on its concept and classification, recording, management, and sovereign credit rating.

Concept and classification. Public debt refers to government borrowing from individuals, financial institutions or other countries in order to finance budget deficits when government expenditures surpass revenue collection. Debt could be classified as *internal* and *external*.

Internal debt is described as government borrowing within a home country through loans, bonds, treasury bills and other means. Since the internal public debt is also called borrowing “within the family” thus “all transactions connected with an internal debt resolve themselves into a series of transfers of wealth within the community” (Jain, 1989 p.12). In another words, the internal public debt is referred to the redistribution of public wealth within one country, so it doesn't have an additional direct money burden on the economy. However, in the case on internal debt a direct real burden on the community takes place. The direct real burden is related to economic welfare loss. If poor taxpayers service the public debt through indirect taxes while debt holders are generally rich and proportionately contribute lower indirect taxes, internal public debt may involve a wealth transfer from poor to rich. Moreover, if “taxation required for servicing the debt checks production and reduces taxpayers’ ability and desire to work and save” internal debts involve an indirect burden (Jain, 1989 p.13).

A country's borrowing from abroad is called *external* borrowing and done through the means of bilateral (agreement that includes one lender and one borrower) and multilateral (agreement that include one borrower and multiple lenders)

borrowing, World Bank borrowing and financial markets. Since external debt involves wealth transfer from the borrowing country to the foreign lender particularly in terms of interest repayment, direct money burden on whole community takes place. In addition, governments have to cover the amount of interest paid on external debt by heavy taxation thus creating direct real burden on the community. Finally, external debt involves indirect burden due to “any checks to production due to the taxation required to meet the debt charges” (Jain, 1989 p.13). Thus, even though any type of debt represents a burden to the economy, external debt is considered to be more burdensome compared to the internal (see Figure 4) (Debt Instrument, 2016).

Figure 4. Public debt classification.

Self-made figure based on the knowledge of this chapter.

Regardless whether the public debt is internal or external, there is also classification of the debt related to its maturity. *Short-term* debt is called the debt that matures with less than one-year period. It is a low interest rate and it may be used for temporary budget deficit coverage. *Medium-term* debt has a maturity within one to five years and has a reasonable interest rate. *Long-term* debt has a maturity over five years and is used mostly for development projects and debt retirement (Debt Instrument, 2016).

Governments issue several types of debt instruments such as treasury bills (T-bills), notes and bonds which are summarized in the flowing figure.

Figure 5. Debt instruments.

Self-made figure based on Debt Instrument, 2016, retrieved from <http://www.investopedia.com/terms/d/debtinstrument.asp>

After addressing the public debt concept and classification according to the internal / external and the maturity standards and after shedding light in the debt instruments, I will now examine the public debt recording.

Public debt recording. There are several internationally recognized ways to record the public debt. *Gross domestic* and *foreign debt* is recorded as a summation of

an entire outstanding public debt both in local and foreign currencies. *Public sector deposits* are deposits in commercial banks that are made by the public sector. *Net domestic debt* is recorded as a deduction of public sector deposits from the gross domestic debt amount. Thus, *net total debt* is a summation of the gross foreign debt and the net total debt. The following Figure 6 depicts the way a country records its debt.

Figure 6. Public debt recording.

Self-made figure based on the knowledge of this chapter.

To better assess the public debt, the economists record it as a percentage of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) which would be discussed later. Now, what about the public debt management?

Public debt management .Regardless the type and structure of a public debt, it is unfortunately common to many countries and a burden to many economies.

Fewer than ten countries around the world live debt-free. The major challenge is not

any more to minimize the size of the public debt but to maintain its sustainable level. The following section will discuss the public debt management.

According to the International Monetary Fund, “Sovereign debt management is the process of establishing and executing a strategy for the government's debt in order to raise the required amount of funding, achieve its risk and cost objectives, and to meet any other sovereign debt management goals the government may have set, such as developing and maintaining an efficient market for government securities” (International Monetary Fund, 2001.p. 2).

Nowadays, policy makers have to be sure that the public debt level and growth rate are sustainable and a country is able to meet its cost and risk objectives while servicing the debt. Sovereign debt should be well structured in terms of interest rate, currency and maturity. The debt portfolio of the government is the largest portfolio of a country. Since it contains risky and complex structures it is a subject to high risks. Thus, having a sound debt structure reduces various risks, such as currency, interest rate and other risks. In addition, country’s debt structure should correspond with monetary, fiscal and exchange rate policies. The important indicators of a public debt include public debt to GDP ratio (International Monetary Fund, 2001).

GDP is all produced domestically goods and services expressed in a monetary value. It is calculated yearly and generally summarizes all of the national economic activity (see Figure 7).

$$\text{GDP} = \text{C} + \text{I} + \text{G} + \text{NX}$$

Where:

- C = Private consumption
- I = A country's total investment
- G = Total government spending
- NX = Difference between export and import

Figure 7. The gross domestic product (GDP)

Self-made box based on Gross Domestic Product - GDP, 2016, retrieved from <http://www.investopedia.com/terms/g/gdp.asp>

The Lebanese GDP is depicted in dollars and could be stated in either real or nominal values, where real *GDP* equals *nominal GDP* adjusted for the level of inflation.

The *Debt-to-GDP ratio* compares what country owes in terms of what it produces. Presented as a percentage, the ratio indicates a country's ability to pay back its debt. There is no a specific debt-to-GDP ratio that is considered ideal. However, if a country is able to pay its debts without harming the development of its economy, the level of debt is considered to be sustainable. With a higher debt-to-GDP ratio, a country's ability to pay its external debt is decreasing thus leading investors to look for higher interest rates, because the risk of default is high (Gross Domestic Product - GDP, 2016).

Sovereign credit rating. Whenever a government makes a decision to issue a security and borrow from public, credit rating agencies perform a credit risk analysis of a sovereign government and assign a rating. According to Standard & Poor's (S&P's) rating services, sovereign rating is an independent, comparable and forward looking opinion of the "creditworthiness of a sovereign government, where

creditworthiness encompasses likelihood of default and credit stability” (Schineller, 2014 p.5).

Nevertheless, a credit rating does not represent a country’s risk as a recommendation to buy, sell or hold a particular debt instrument, measure of volatility, liquidity, or a market value of any financial instruments. S&P’s has rated 129 sovereign states worldwide.

After the process of analysis is completed, rating is assigned in terms of a letter-scale that ranges from the highest rating of AAA (the obligator’s capacity to meet the commitment is extremely strong) to SD/D (the lowest capacity to meet obligations with high risk of a default). S&P’s also issues comments regarding a particular rating. In addition to S&P’s there are two more internationally recognized rating agencies – Moody’s and Fitch. Nearly 95% of the rating business is controlled by those three credit rating firms (Cullinan & Jelencovic, 2015; Schineller, 2014).

Public Debt Sustainability Analysis

According to Blominvest Bank research (2015), the IMF suggests that the public debt should be analyzed in relative terms rather than absolute terms. This means that “the level of debt should be assessed against the size of the economy and against the ability of the country to pay back its dues” (Daou & Mikhael, 2015).

Thus, having a sustainable debt does not always mean that reduction of debt-to-GDP ratio should be made. Sometimes, if a particular level of debt-to-GDP ratio of a country remains stable or even declines, the debt considered sustainable since it could be reimbursed and further accumulation could be avoided. Regarding factors affecting the level of public debt in a country see Figure 8.

Figure 8. Factors affecting the level of public debt in a country.

Self-made figure based on the knowledge of this chapter.

Hence, a high growth of real GDP while controlling the level of inflation measures the country's ability to create enough resources to satisfy the country's need while paying back its debts. The nation's effective interest rate is linked to international rates and to the country's level of risk (sovereign credit rating). Consequently, higher interest rates lead to the higher interest payments, thus increasing the debt burden. If fiscal and primary balances result in a deficit, the country covers it by obtaining more debt, leading the country into a cycle of indebtedness that could negatively affect the health of the whole economy.

However, when a country suffers high level of public debt, it might use two tools to address the burden: - Paris club and liability management.

Paris club. If a country is in trouble and its level of debt is considered unsustainable, the help of international community could be obtained. *Paris Club* is a

set of creditors that participate in renegotiation or reduction of sovereign debts terms. The Club includes 19 constant members: United States, United Kingdom, Austria, Australia, Belgium, Canada, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Netherlands, Norway, Russia, Spain, Sweden and Switzerland. Other creditor countries participate based on an ad-hoc basis.

The Paris Club is not a formal institution but the set of rules and regulations about the debt relief that are determined by its member-countries. Since it is an informal institute, the Paris Club meeting outcome doesn't result in the legal agreement between a debtor and creditor countries. The meeting results with signature of a so-called "Agreed Minutes". Those minutes recommend the debtor nation sign an agreement with creditor nations thus forming a bilateral agreement.

Since 1956 when the first sovereign debt restructuring deals took place, the Paris Club reached 429 agreements involving 90 debtor countries (Weiss, 2014). Lebanon was one of the debtor countries that look for the Paris Club help with its debt restructuring. In 2002 and 2007, Paris II and Paris III Conferences, respectively, took place. The details related to those meetings are discussed in chapter 4.

One of the outcomes of a Paris club meeting could be a *swap of debt maturities* that takes place when a debtor wishes to decrease an interest rate burden. In this case, a debtor buys the outstanding (usually short-term) debt that has higher interest rate and issues new debt instruments with longer (or the same) maturity and a lower interest rate (Weiss, 2014). *Debt swap* is an instrument of liability management that will be discussed in the following part.

Liability management. Liability management is one of the debt management instruments that strengthen the fiscal sustainability and anticipate financial crises. There are two of instruments that are involved: *buybacks* and *swaps* of the debt. In

this part we will pay particular attention to the *debt swaps* as this instrument was used by the Lebanese government during post-war periods (Weiss, 2014). The major objectives of a liability management are depicted in the Figure 9.

Since the liability management lies under the broader category of public debt management, its instruments should be enacted under the high supervision of government authorities. Also, those operations should be coordinated with both, monetary and fiscal, policies.

Moreover, since the main objective of a debt swap is to lower the debt service payments, it is performed in the following way. A country retires and replaced high-coupon debt with the lower-coupon debt and it is called a *high-coupon refunding*. Debt swap techniques were commonly used in 2006 and 2007 by many developing countries, such as Brazil, Russia, Turkey, Lebanon and many others.

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After having addressed so far the public finance and its items, mainly the public revenues, expenses and budget, the public debt, and the public debt sustainability analysis, it is now time to talk about the balance of payments and the remittances.

Figure 9. Liability management.

Self-made figure based on Medeiros et al. (2007), World Bank (2015), and OECD (2003).

Remittances

In order to be able to finance their economies, the authorities of any country rely on the budget, public debt, foreign direct investment (FDI), official development assistance (ODA), and remittances. This part deals with remittances regarding the development financing, their definition and characteristics, the Global Financial Crisis and remittances, their benefits and their recording.

Remittances and the Development Financing

Most developing countries require additional, cross-border funds for their development. In addition, most of these countries have a high migration rate to developed countries from where their migrants constantly send money back home.

Recent researches consider these remittances inflows as a great source that receiving countries may use for their development (De Bruyn & Wets, n.d; Ketkar & Ratha, 2008; World Bank, 2005). For example, Ketkar and Ratha (2008) suggest the future-flow securitization as a tool for development finance. In addition, researchers agree that remittance inflows usually stable and even countercyclical in many countries (Cohen et al., 2012; Ghobril, 2012; Ketkar & Ratha, 2001). Many researchers state that the impact of remittances is so important a developing country should establish bonds with its Diaspora in order to increase its involvement and the amount of remittances (Hourani, 2007; Okonjo-Iweala & Ratha 2011; Agunais & Newland, 2012; Jamali & Lanteri, 2015). Also, some of the researchers talk about use of remittances as a part of securitization deals (Gammage, 2005; Hughes, 2011).

The following part of this chapter will summarize this research. It defines remittances, their characteristics and benefits, and their global trends during the global financial crisis. I will also take a look at the securitization deals, particularly future-

flow securities using remittances. The scheme of a remittances backed securities will provide an understanding of how a country may borrow internationally using its remittance inflows.

Definition and Characteristics

Generally, remittances are funds that are sent by emigrants to their country of origin (OECD, 2014). According to Balance of Payment (BOP) Methodology of Lebanon, remittances include “all current transfers carried out between migrants working in their new economy and their country of origin” taking into consideration that fact that the migrants should reside in the new country for at least one year (Balance of Payment Methodology, 2013, p.3). However, legal transfers do not include transfers that are informal, unofficial or illegal.

Remittances are considered the largest source of external financing and one of the main contributors to GDP of developing countries. Studies revealed that remittances play a very important economic role in many countries. For example, remittance inflow is a major source of revenue to countries such as the Republic of Yemen, Bangladesh and many South Asian countries (Cohen et al., 2012). The Figure 10 shows external sources of financing an economy.

Over the past decade remittances were constantly increasing, surpassing FDI and ODA. Migrants’ remittances are considered stable and constantly increasing over time. Also they are less volatile than ODA, FDI and debt. In addition, remittances tend to be higher in developing countries. The following Figure 11 supports this fact.

Figure 10. External sources of financing an economy.

Self-made figure based on External finance, debt and foreign direct investment- UNCTAD (2014).

Figure 11. Remittances and other external financing.

Note. from World Bank, April 2015, retrieved from <https://siteresources.worldbank.org/>

After having showed the importance of remittances in development financing, the next writings will shed light on the remittances and the Global Financial Crisis (2007-2010).

Remittances and the Global Financial Crisis

The Global Financial Crisis did not greatly impact the stability of expatriates' money inflows. However, authors agree that remittances, unlike other capital inflows, are mostly stable and sometimes even countercyclical. Agunais and Newland (n.d.) stated that since the financial crisis took place, remittances tend to be relatively more stable than ODA and FDI, thus particularly helpful to developing countries. Moreover, Sirkeci et al. (2012) found that remittances tend to be resilient during the crisis due to the following five broad patterns (see Figure 12).

In this regard, the Lebanese local studies generally agreed that the global financial crisis had no negative effect on expatriates' remittances in Lebanon. In addition, the researchers agree that the remittances flow into Lebanon offset the negative economic effects of the global financial crisis (De Bruyn & Wets, n.d.; Ghobril, 2012).

After having addressed the remittances and the Global Financial Crisis, the following lines will discuss the benefits of remittances.

Figure 12. Remittances resiliency patterns against the Global Financial Crisis.

Self-made figure based on Cohen et al. (2012).

Benefits of Remittances

Recent researches mostly concentrate on the remittance flow to developing countries, giving the developed countries less attention. This is due to the effect on poverty and potential for development. According to Agunais and Newland (n.d.), remittances are considered one of the most tangible links between development and migration. Not only they are great source of foreign exchange for the BOP account but they also promote macroeconomic stability, increase investments, reduce poverty and promote access to education and health (see Figure 13).

Figure 13. Benefits of remittances in an economy.

Self-made figure based on De Bruyn and Wets (n.d.).

On the *households' level* remittances provide basic need for poor people, enhancing opportunity for obtaining education and accessing healthcare. Also, remittances provide saving and investment opportunities for receiving families in addition to emergency resources during war or natural disasters. On *community and regional levels* remittances boost local economic and finance local development projects. Finally, on *macro level*, remittances represent stable and counter-cyclical inflow remittances. Therefore, they improve the BOP by providing the foreign exchange (Bruyn & Wets, n.d.). Finally, the next session deals with the remittances recording.

Remittances Recording

Understanding how remittances are recorded is done through addressing the composition of Lebanon's BOP. The Banque du Liban (BDL) methodology in this regard states that the BOP statistical reports "summarize in a methodical way all the

economic transactions that take place between the resident economy and the outside world during the year” (Balance of Payment Methodology, 2013. p 1). Information is reported in millions of US dollars. Transactions that are denominated in other currencies are converted to US dollars based on principal rates. The BOP of Lebanon includes three general sections, the Current Account, Capital Account, and Net Errors and Omissions (see Figure 14).

Current account section includes activities that take place between resident and non-resident economies in means of goods, services, income, and current account transfers. *The services section* within current account section includes transportation, travel, insurance and other services. *Income section* consists of compensation to employees and investment income from direct investment, portfolio investment and other investment related to BDL’s income, government investment and commercial banks’ paid and received investment income. The *Current Transfers Section* consists of current monetary payment made by foreign governments and international organizations or contribution to international organizations regularly paid by the Lebanese government. This section is divided into general government, workers’ remittances and other transfers.

Capital and financial account section records changes in assets and liabilities regarding nonresident economies. It includes capital account and financial account that records various investments.

The last part of the BOP is ***net errors and omissions***. It keeps unrecorded transactions that take place due to lack of statistics and unreliability of estimations. It contains mainly the liability part of the flows in the items, such as migrants’ transfers, adjustment for external trade payment, insurance, travel and transportation services, foreign-exchange operations, portfolio and direct investments (Balance of Payment

Methodology, 2013). Balance of payment components of Lebanon are shown in Appendix I.

Figure 14. Balance of payment of Lebanon elements.

Self-made figure based on Balance of Payment Methodology, by Banque du Liban, 2013, retrieved from www.bdl.gov.lb

Most important for this study, workers' remittances are recorded in Current Transfers section of the BOP. This includes all current transfers made by migrants that worked in the new economy for at least one year, both debit and credit.

Private transfers from and into Lebanon (transfers by foreigners working in Lebanon and by Lebanese residing abroad) are estimated by adopting an average monthly salary and a saving ratio related to the type of work (workers or managerial staff). The same method is applied to estimate the funds transferred by Lebanese emigrants, in order to obtain the net amount of saved inflows (International Monetary Fund, 2015 p.5).

The external Sector Section of BDL considers that half of all Lebanese residents abroad and half of all foreign workers in Lebanon have full-time work and send their saving to their home-country. The data related to the transfers of expatriates' funds is recorded by International Transactions Reporting System (ITRS) of Lebanon (International Monetary Fund, 2015).

After having addressed the public finance and the remittance, the final section encompasses the securitization.

Securitization

This section will tackle the background of securitization and the securitization of the future flow receivables: asset-backed securities framework and remittances backed securities.

Background of Securitization

Originally, a borrowing entity obtained financing through bank loans, current accounts or other credit facilities, such as bonds, notes, commercial papers and other debt certificates in the capital market. Asset securitization recently became one of the instruments of attaining financing. Figure 15 summarizes the highlights of the securitization.

Securitization is issuing debt security where cash flow generated by a pool of underlying assets pays principal, interest and a participation share. The main difference from traditional forms of financing and securitization is that securitized deals have higher credit rating than the entity's secured debt due to the creation of a pool of assets and the isolation of its cash flows. Thus, originators benefit from lower costs of debt while investors benefit by obtaining investment with lower risk (Bijjani, 2014).

Figure 15. Securitization.

Self-made figure based on Bijjani (2014).

Figure 16. History of securitization.

Self-made figure based on Innovative Financing for Development , by Ketkar & Ratha, 2008, retrieved from <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/>

As shown in Figure 16, prior to World War II, major investors were banks that used to hold their loans till maturity while loans were fully sponsored by depositors. Later, with high demand for housing loans, banks and other financial intermediaries were looking for other ways to increase the sources of the mortgage financing. The first deals of assets securitization took place during the 1970's and involved pooling and reselling mortgages. When the securitization market was developed, guarantees of government agencies encouraged non-mortgage assets securitization. In 1985, issuance of securities backed by car loans took place. Following the boom of the credit card market and increasing confidence in securitization, the issuance of securities backed by credit card payments happened in 1986 enabling originators to borrow 50 million dollars.

The next wave of securitization involved future flow receivables. In Latin America due to the high amount of syndicate loans and high interest rates, a debt crisis took place. In order to restructure existing debt, so called Bradley Bonds were created. With the help of this innovation Latin loans were switched into tradable bonds; this later allowed many developing countries to obtain international financing for development through the bond issuance. However, being more volatile than traditional loans, the bonds made profit-oriented investors, who marked their assets to market on a daily basis, move their investments in bonds from country to country as soon as they sensed a trouble. Thus, developing countries kept looking for innovations that would provide more stable financing. Together with Diaspora bonds and GDP-indexed bonds, future flow securitization was one of the major innovations (Ketkar & Ratha, 2008).

After having defined and set the historical background of securitization, I will tackle now the topic of the securitization of future-flow receivables.

Securitization of Future-Flow Receivables

Future flows receivables are projected cash inflows, in the context of this study to developing countries. Those receivables could be used as underlying assets in securitization deal thus acting as insurance that the borrowed amount would be repaid.

In 1987, first future-flow securitization deal took place in Mexico and involved Telmex, the state-owned telephone company pledging its future telephone payments. Since that time a wide variety of assets were used as underlying assets as part of the securitization schemes. Those types of securities were introduced in large countries like Brazil, Kazakhstan and Turkey as well as small ones like El Salvador and Peru.

The major assets used as underlying are oil and gas, credit cards and other receivables. Remittances are among the top ten those types of assets. \$1.8 billion worth securities were issued during the period 1992 - 2006 (Ketkar & Ratha, 2008).

In order to understand the mechanism of securitization, we will take a detailed look at the framework of the asset backed securitization scheme which is common for various types of assets, including future flow receivables. We will also talk about the remittances backed-securities.

Asset-backed securities framework. Asset-Backed Securitization schemes are subject to the Securities Act of 1933 with its last amendment in 2007. Issuing “Asset-Backed Securities” as a part of securitization scheme requires a set of particular participants. It also involves the transfers of assets to a third party. This third party issues the securities. Thus, several elements are involved in issuing the asset-backed securities. Figure 17 summarizes them all.

Originator. It is a party that is willing to transfer its assets in a securitization transaction. The originator may be an incorporated public company, a corporation or

any other entity approved for such deals. The amount of money that an originator is willing to purchase could be limited to the amount of ten percent of the total value of remittance inflows to a country, like in case of Kenya (Ntalami & Waruingi, 2007).

Origination fees. Commissions and fees paid within a securitization deal that may include rating fees and other professional fees to those who participate in such transactions.

Figure 17. Asset-backed securities elements.

Self-made figure based on the knowledge of this chapter.

Issuer. It is an entity that offers to the public asset backs securities. Title, interest, rights and obligations in the assets shall be transferred by the originator to the issues. Thus, an originator is not retaining any liabilities or beneficiary interests over the underlying assets.

Credit rating. Any securitization deal should have an independent and objective opinion on its creditworthiness. Since the result of the scheme is the debt instrument, it should be rated according to the relevant risk factors. Usually, credit rating agencies like Standard & Poor's, Moody's and Fitch rate securitization deals.

Trustee may be an institution or a person that insures the rights of the ABSs (asset-backed securities) holders. A trustee receives "product payment" and pays principal and interest to the investors while sending the excessive funds to the originator.

Servicing agent is appointed by an originator and independent of the issues, acts on behalf of the originator and responsible for bookkeeping, statements and records involved in the securitization deal.

In addition, an originator shall hire an *advisor* among investment banks, brokers or investment advisors in order to facilitate the offer, issue and listing of the ABS. Then, an originator should submit to an authority a prescribed form of application for approval of the transaction of securitization and listing ABSs. The terms and conditions of the proposed structure together with the set of required documents should be attached to the application.

Regarding the underlying *assets*, they should be able to generate "a true and identifiable revenue stream that is projected to be sufficient to service the return of and return on investment as well as allowable expenses for the life of the asset backed securities". In addition, the transfers shall be free and transferred at a fair value (Ntalami & Waruingi, 2007).

After having addressed the asset-backed securities framework, the following writings will talk about the Future-Flow Securitization Scheme.

Future-flow securitization scheme. The originator (borrower in a developing country) waves the rights to collect future receivables that come from sending country (designated customers) to a Special Purpose Vehicle (SPV) that is located offshore. SPV issues debt and sells bonds to investors transferring proceeds to the borrowing country. A trustee (collection account) insures the principal and interest payments to the investors while sending excess collection back to the originator. Thus, the borrower should service the securitized bond on time. Since the whole structure is designed to take place offshore, it “ensures that the hard currency receivable does not enter the country until bondholders have been paid” (Ketkar & Ratha, 2008 p.27). Figure 18 demonstrates the basic scheme of a future-flow securitization including all of its major participants.

Figure 18. Future-flow securitization scheme.

Reprinted from Innovative financing for development, p.27, by Ketkar & Ratha, 2008, retrieved from <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/>

The asset-backed securitization structure will be studied more in depth through using remittances as collateral in the following section.

Remittance-backed securities. In order to be used as an underlying asset, the asset should be a reliable revenue stream of money that could be predictable and stable over the life of the structured asset-backed security. Thus, remittances might be used as underlying assets. Many developing countries, such as Brazil and Mexico, use remittances in order to obtain international funds. The following paragraphs will shed light on the securitization using remittances inflow issued by Brazil.

In 2002, Brazil was able to raise \$450 million through its first future-flow securitization. The structure of the Banco do Brasil remittances securitization is depicted in the following figure.

Figure 19. Future-flow securitization scheme.

Reprinted from Innovative financing for development, p.41, by Ketkar & Ratha, 2008, retrieved from <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/>

The figure depicts remittances securitization deal created by Banco do Brasil (BdB), state-owned bank. In this deal BdB acts as originator and sells its future remittances flow from Brazilian workers in Japan to an offshore SPV located in the Cayman Islands. The amount of deal is USD 250 million and its rating is BBB+ against sovereign rating of BB-. The New York-based trust acts as a trustee to insure the interests of investors. Proceeds of USD 250 million were transferred to the originator through the SPV. Remittances from Japan are collected by the trust. When the principal and interest payment are made, excess collection reaches Brazil.

The whole deal takes place offshore. Remittances enter Brazil through the Trust and SPV when the principal and interest payments to the investors are made. The securitization deal is rated higher than the sovereign rating since the structure mitigates several risks. It mitigates sovereign *transfer and convertibility risks* (risk of government prevention of convertibility of a local currency into foreign, and vice versa) since remittances didn't enter Brazil but were moved offshore. In addition, the structure mitigates bankruptcy risk.

Nevertheless, several risks remain - performance risk (the willingness of BdB to transfer remittances through SPV and trust), product risk (the ability of Japan to generate remittances), and diversion risk (the possibility of reselling remittances to another party by BdB). However, all those risks were minimized. The credit rating agencies took into consideration that the originator (BdB) is the largest bank in Brazil, that it was established in Japan in 1972, and that the government of Brazil is dependent on foreign currency generation through remittances. In addition, overcollateralization with a 7.64x ratio of debt service coverage mitigated the product risk derived from volatility and seasonal fluctuation in remittances inflows (Ketkar & Ratha, 2008).

While discussing the remittances securitization scheme of Brazil, the benefits and obstacles of remittances securitization and public debt were mentioned. The following writings will elaborate these elements (See Figure 20).

Benefits and obstacles of remittances securitization. Major benefits of borrowing through remittances securitization are access to international markets, lower cost of debt and longer maturities.

Figure 20. Remittances securitization opportunities and obstacles.

Self-made figure based on the knowledge in this chapter.

International market access. Most of the developing countries lack credit history thus creating a perception that investing in them is risky (Ketkar & Ratha, 2008). A securitization structure allows sovereign and private entities in developing countries to break through the credit rating ceiling and get international financing. For

example, research by Agunais and Newland (n.d.) revealed that the perfect candidates that may benefit from securitization are those whose sovereign credit rating is “up to five notches below investment grade” and have substantial receivables. The major advantage of securitization use by developing countries is obtaining an investment grade rating BBB- to such transactions. This takes place due to heavy overcollateralization with the only chance of default as a result of slowdown of remittances inflow by more than 95 percent. The typical structure of securitization allows issuers (particularly in developing countries) to lift the sovereign rating ceiling and receive financing at a much lower interest rate and longer maturity.

Lower cost of debt. Those transactions are also appealing since they reduce borrowing cost. Investors are attracted to this asset class since the securitization of remittances has rarely failed (only couple of defaults on remittance-backed securities, RBSs has been recorded). This asset class performed very well during several crises, such as debt defaults in Russia and Ecuador (1998-1999), liquidity crisis in Asia (1997-1998) and peso crisis in Mexico (1994-1995). Mitigation of risk and enhancement of credit takes place due to sustainable collateral, diversification of risk through many investors and the third parties guarantees. Since the borrower cannot access the future-flow assets unless it pays its due, the structure mitigates convertibility and transfer risks. Also, the bankruptcy risk is mitigated since the SPV does not have another creditor and cannot go bankrupt (though the risk of the originator’s bankruptcy still exists). In addition, smaller average spreads and lower volatility in spread and price characterize future-flow securities. When a speculative sovereign obtains investment-grade transaction the debt can be bought by increased numbers of institutional investors thus substantially reducing the spread.

As an example of the securitization of Brazil in 2002 that was held by the state owned Banco du Brazil, the deal had an investment grade by Moody's (Baa1) and S&P's (BBB+) compared to the nation's sovereign rating of B1 and BB-, respectively. In addition, many other Brazilian banks got engaged in securitization while 10 out of 24 transactions were rated AAA. According to available data, these transaction saved originators over 700 basis points (Suhas & Ratha, 2008). Authors also provide several examples of different countries that have issued remittance-backed securities from the perspective of their sovereign rating vis-à-vis the rating of securitization transaction. The following Table 1 demonstrates that.

Table 1

Remittance-backed Transaction Ratings

Year	Issuer	Amount (US\$ millions)	Transaction rating	Sovereign rating	Rating gain (no. of notches)
2007	Banco Bradesco, Brazil	400	A-	BB	5
2005	Banco de Credito del Peru	50	BBB	BB+	2
2004	Banco Salvadoreno	25	BBB	BB+	2
2002	Banco do Brasil	250	BBB+	BB-	5
1998	Banco Cuscatlan, El Salvador	50	BBB	BB	3

Note. Table reprinted from *Innovative financing for development*, p.43, by Ketkar & Ratha, 2008, retrieved from <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/>

Longer debt maturities. Securitization of future-flow securities allows developing countries target wider class of investors than unsecured deals. For example, investment grade attracts insurance companies that tend to buy and hold any asset until maturity. In addition, by establishing a credit history by borrowing through securitization, developing countries will be able to access international markets in the future and even decrease the cost of the access. Finally, some developing counties

may be able to access international capital markets only through future-flow securities (Ketkar & Ratha, 2008).

In addition to international capital market access, lower cost and extended maturities issuers of remittance backed securities may also benefit from several externalities. Agunais and Newland (n.d.) suggest that securitization of remittances flow is beneficial to developing countries. The authors noted two broad policy trends related to remittances, such as strengthening infrastructure in order to support remittances and more productive use of remittances through securitizing remittance flows and cross selling products that are linked to remittances (Agunais and Newland, n.d.). In addition, Ketkar and Ratha (2008) mention that reforms related to the legal and institutional environment due to creation of securitization deals facilitate development of domestic capital markets and encouraged international placement especially in the early 1990s.

The main obstacles in raising funds through future-flow receivables are the absence of a clear law and high cost of such transaction. The originator country must have a clear bankruptcy law. In addition, legal and other fixed costs are high. Obtaining a credit rating of the transaction is costly and represents an example of a fixed cost. However, the International Finance Corporation and World Bank educate government official or private borrowers and assist in preparation of future-flow-securitization deals (Ketkar & Ratha 2008).

After having addressed the opportunities and benefits of remittances securitization, I will deal with the remittance securitization and public debt.

Remittances securitization and public debt. Little research has directly addressed to the use of RBSs proceeds as a source to finance a country's public debt. In addition, authors do not always mention how exactly those proceeds were used.

Nevertheless, due to the fact that expatriates' remittances represent the flow of future receivable that could be collateralized to access additional capital, securitization is the alternative method to finance *public debt*.

According Okonjo-Iweala and Ratha (2011), when a migrant transfers foreign currency to a relative's creditworthy bank in his home country, the bank pays out the remittance from its holding of local currency. That transaction creates a foreign currency asset equivalent to the size of the remittance, which can be used as collateral for borrowing cheaply and over the long term in overseas capital markets. Such borrowing has no effect on the flow of money from migrants to their beneficiaries. Yet development banks, national banks in developing countries and donor agencies can partner to harness enough remittances and create enough collateral to raise significant sums of money to invest in agriculture, roads, housing and other vital projects.

Potentially, many countries are able to issue remittances-backed bonds up to 10-20 percent of the annual flow of remittances. According to Ketkar and Ratha (2008) estimates based on the total amount of remittances, the issuing ability of remittance-receiving countries and a 5:1 ratio of overcollateralization, all major recipients of large amounts of remittances have potential of securitization at nearly 10 percent of the total amount of the remittances inflow.

Summary

In this chapter the literature related to the public finance, remittances and securitization have been collected and analyzed. First, public finance has been explored from several angles. We have defined the public debt, its classification, recording and management by the government. We also have determined how international credit rating agencies assess sovereign riskiness in terms of the public

debt. In addition, we have taken a look at the debt sustainability analysis and ways of how heavily indebted countries manage their debt through the help of international communities and the debt management techniques, such as debt swaps and buybacks.

The second part of the chapter have explored the topic of remittances through their definition and characteristics, benefits for receiving countries and the way of recording them. We also have discovered remittances use for the development financing and their behavior during the Global Financial Crisis. In order to link the public debt with the remittances inflows we have explored the topic of securitization. Beginning with the history of securitization, we have discovered the technical parts of asset-backed securities creation including its major participants, analyzed the basic securitization scheme, provided remittance-backed security example of Brazil. We have ended this chapter discussion by mentioning the benefits and obstacles of RBSs concluding with final section that talks about the link of remittances securitization and the public debt financing.

Finally, Figure 21 will establish a model linking all this theoretical knowledge that would help in understanding how to finance the public debt of Lebanon with remittances backed securities in chapter 4 – The Results.

Local resources, international private resources, and securitization finance the national economy of a country. Among the international private resources, the remittances of foreign workers residing in foreign countries which are transferred to their families in their home countries are crucial in financing an economy. However, as Lebanon is heavily indebted, remittances finance the economy on community and regional levels. Nevertheless, the remittances should not only provide foreign exchange on a BOP level; in addition, and on a macro level, they should also be securitized to finance the public debt.

Figure 21. Financing theoretically public debt with remittance-backed securities.

Self-made figure based on all the knowledge of this chapter.

How can Lebanon realize the remittances securitization? Chapter four will answer this question. But before, chapter three will define the paradigm and methodology to bridge this theoretical model of remittances-backed securities with the practical case study of Lebanon.

CHAPTER 3

RESEARCH PARADIGM AND METHODOLOGY

The literature review dealt with and analyzed theoretically the public finance, remittances, and securitization. The objective was to use remittance-backed securities in order to finance the public debt of a country instead of relying mainly on the budget and public resources. All the theoretical knowledge that was used in chapter two was modeled in order to be exploited in chapter four to use remittance-backed securities in financing the huge net public debt of the small Lebanese economy.

However, after having dressed a theoretical model in this regard, and in order to prove practically the problem statement of this thesis, financing the Lebanese public debt with remittance-backed securities, four hypotheses will be tested as follows:

- H₁: There is a need for Lebanon to obtain financing from international markets.
- H₂: There is a way to get financing through remittance-backed securities.
- H₃: There is a potential borrowing method from international markets using remittances inflows to Lebanon.
- H₄: There are benefits for Lebanon from borrowing through remittance-backed securities.

The research will substantiate these hypotheses using the post-positivism. Such paradigm uses mainly the quantitative methodology relying on a statistical analysis which uses several tools such as time series and regressions. Finally, the analytic narrative will be used to read and analyze the time series.

The Research Paradigm: Post-positivism

A paradigm is a philosophical way of viewing the world. Post-positivism means that a reality exists but it can be imperfectly known because of the researcher's human limitations. Its foundations are objectivity, generalizability, and understanding a probable, not a certain reality.

This paradigm uses quantification, sophisticated statistical methods, and mathematical models to demonstrate hypotheses but it does not enable the attainment of scientifically provable insights. These research tools cannot produce valid empirical evidence and a theoretically relevant interpretation. They need discussion especially in empirical studies and will never be a substitute for theoretical elaboration. Consequently, post-positivism deals with the quality of the input data, the use of a more integrated approach, and the context of the studied phenomenon (Adam, 2014). As this paradigm relies mainly on quantitative methodology, the following writings will explain this methodology.

Quantitative Methodology

Cohen and Manion (1980) defined quantitative research as a social research using empirical methods and empirical statements. Moreover, and according to Creswell (1994), such a methodology explains phenomenon by collecting and analyzing numerical data through using mathematically based methods, mainly statistics. Based on these two definitions, this research collected and analyzed secondary quantitative data in order to show how to use remittance-backed securities to finance the net public debt of Lebanon.

Hence, the following paragraphs will elaborate on the collected quantitative databases, their statistical treatment, and their way of narration in order to move from data to information.

The Collected Quantitative Databases

The collected databases are considered as secondary data. They consisted of the following times series elements: GDP of Lebanon (1993-2015) in billion USD, net public debt of Lebanon (1993-2015), remittances of Lebanese workers (2002-2015) (Lebanon GDP, 2016; BDL, 2016; BDL, 2017).

Regarding the GDP of Lebanon, the figures were in USD. For the purposes of this research, they were converted to billion USD. The net public debt of Lebanon at the end of period (December of each year) was collected in billion LBP and converted into billion USD through using the rate USD 1 = LBB 1507.5 (the BDL exchange rate). For the purposes of this research, I calculated the net Debt/GDP ratio as a percentage. Finally, the remittances were only available at the Central Bank of Lebanon website for the monthly period of 2002-2014 in million USD. For the purposes of this research, I made the sum for each year in order to present this data in a yearly way. Also, I deducted remittances outflows from inflows in order to present the net figures. The following paragraphs will show how these databases were integrated in order to show how the relatively stable and crisis resilient remittances if securitized will finance the net public debt of Lebanon.

Time Series

All the collected databases had to be statistically treated in order to move from data to information. But before, these time series will be historically read in chapter four and linked to international and national events. Moreover, this research will use the time series additive model with the monthly remittances statistics (January 2002-December 2014). The procedure will deliver a linear and adjusted model to predict the adjusted monthly remittances for 2015 and to prove that these remittances are

relatively stable and resilient to crisis despite some variations from time to time.

However, the times series additive model consists of several steps (see Figure 22).

Figure 22. The time series additive model: 11 steps of monthly remittances (2002-20014).

Self-made figure based on Spiegel & Stephen (2014).

Another statistical method is used for net public debt and GDP. It consists of the regression.

Regression

Regression investigates the relationships between or among quantitative (numeric) variables. When undertaking a regression analysis, the investigator assembles data related to the variables under study. Therefore, the regression analysis will estimate the quantitative causal effect of the independent variable (s) on the dependent variable. The way to do it is to reach a simple or a multiple regression model.

The multiple regression model explains the effect of several independent quantitative (numeric) variables (x_i) over one dependent quantitative (numeric) variable (y). The first step is to compute a coefficient of correlation R which formula is:

$$r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i y_i) - n(\bar{x})(\bar{y})}{\sqrt{\left[\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i^2) - n(\bar{x})^2 \right] \left[\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i^2) - n(\bar{y})^2 \right]}}$$

The coefficient of correlation $|r|$ is then interpreted based on its absolute value. r is weak ($0 \leq |r| < 0.5$), average ($0.5 \leq |r| < 0.7$), or strong ($0.7 \leq |r| \leq 1$).

When $|r|$ is strong, this means that the multiple regression model will be strong based on the following equation or multiple regression model:

$$y = a_1 x_1 + a_2 x_2 + \dots + a_n x_n + b \text{ (constant)}$$

Moreover, a and b formulas are as follows:

$$a = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i y_i) - n(\bar{x})(\bar{y})}{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i)^2 - n(\bar{x})^2}$$

$$b = \bar{y} - a \bar{x}$$

However, the simple or linear regression model is a particular case of the multiple regression as it studies the causal effect of an independent quantitative variable (numeric) (x) over another dependent quantitative (numeric) variable (y). It allows drawing a scatter diagram which shows the dispersion of (x_i, y_i) in the space (see Figure 23).

Figure 23. The scatted diagram.

Reprinted from An introduction to regression analysis, by Sykes, 1993. Retrieved from <http://chicagounbound.uchicago.edu/>

The simple regression model is written in the following equation:

$$y = ax + b \text{ (constant)}$$

Once, all this work is done, a final step is to perform the assessment of the statistical significance or the generalizability of this estimated relationship based on the p-value for each a_i or the statistical error in the Normal distribution which should be $\leq 5\%$ or 0.05.

Finally, the main objective of the regression model is not only to study the causal relationship among quantitative (numeric) variables but also to make forecasts.

These forecasts would be very accurate if $|r|$ is strong and therefore the value of “a” is high (Sykes, 1993).

In chapter 4 or the results, two simple regression models will be done. The first one will be between the net public debt and time for the period 1993-2015. Its equation will be theoretically as follows:

$$\text{Net total debt} = a * \text{year} + b$$

This equation shows how net total debt is varying across time. It leads also to forecasting the net total debt for the period 2016-2025.

The second linear regression model will be between the net total debt and the GDP for the period 1993-2015. Its equation will be theoretically as follows:

$$\text{Net total debt} = a * \text{GDP} + b$$

Rewriting this equation differently leads to forecasting the GDP for and consequently based on the forecasts of the net total debt for the period 2016-2025. Therefore, the equation serving for forecasting is as follows:

$$\text{GDP} = (\text{Net total debt} - b) / a$$

Finally, the multiple regression model will study the net total debt according to GDP and remittances through the following equation:

$$\text{Net total debt} = a_1 * \text{GDP} + a_2 * \text{Remittances} + b$$

Computing time series and regression models means a partial move from data to information. To fulfill this move, analytic narrative should be used in order to analyze these time series.

Analytic Narrative

Bates, Greif, Levi, Rosenthal and Weingast published their book *Analytic Narratives* in 1998 in which they stated that “the best form of analysis combines the analytic tools of political science and economics with the narrative tools of history. In

additional to the narrative record, authors should seek parsimony, refinement and mathematical elegance. The concept that theory linked to data is more powerful than either theory or data alone” (Bates et al., 2016).

A narrative reports human actions and resulting events in a clear temporal order of these actions. Thus they will be more intelligible to the public. Analytic narrative is nowadays a tag in the political economy literature as it is at the crossroads of economics, politics, and history. Hence, analytic narrative is more than telling a story with significant theoretical underpinnings. Some authors consider it as a new approach to history which reconciles the narrative mode of this discipline with the model-building activity of theoretical economics and politics.

However, there are four ideal-types of analytic narratives: alternation, hybridation, hypothesis-testing, and supplementation. Nevertheless, a convincing analytic narrative is rooted into traditional history. Once the light is shed on a problem, which was neglected by the historians, it should attract historians to make adequate their inadequate records thanks to the solution that arrived at analytically to be double-checked (Mongin, 2009).

Summary

The literature review chapter sketched a theoretical model to use the remittance-backed securities to finance the public debt of a country. In order to test and prove such a model in Lebanon, this epistemological chapter dressed the problems statement and four hypotheses. If proved, these hypotheses will lead to:

- Understand the structure and development of the Lebanese public debt.
- Determine possibilities of leveraging remittances impact by financing the public debt through remittance-backed securities.
- Create a Lebanese model of the international borrowing using remittances.

- Analyze advantages, disadvantage and obstacles of that model.

In order to test these hypotheses, a post-positivist paradigm is used. The selected paradigm relies mainly on time series, simple, and multiple regression models, and inferential statistics in order to check the causality relation among quantitative variables such as the net total debt, GDP, time, and remittances. This would also allow the researcher to predict the values of these economic aggregates for the period 2016-2025 and not only to be confined to the period 2002-2014 for the remittances and 1993-2015 for the rest of the economic indicators. Finally, Figure 24 sketches the link between the literature review and the field.

Figure 24. Linking the theoretical remittance-backed securities to the Lebanese economy.

Self-made figure based on the knowledge in chapters 2 and 3.

In order to do so, the following chapter will dive into the Lebanese economy ex ante, during, and ex post war to show its evolution especially when it comes to the dramatic growth of the public debt. Such growth and remittances will be also read through time and local economic and political crisis and international donors' conferences to help Lebanon. Moreover, such growth will be also read through the regional events [Gulf wars, Arab Turmoil (2011), etc.] and the Global Financial Crisis or the Big Slump (2007-2010). This will lead to sketching a practical model of remittance-backed securities to finance the public debt of Lebanon.

Finally, comparing both theoretical and practical models in chapter five or the conclusion of this thesis leads to establishing a final model of remittance-backed securities to finance the net total debt of Lebanon relying on theory and on practice and relying on epistemology. In order to do so, let us move to chapter four or the results of this research.

CHAPTER 4

FIELD WORK AND FINDINGS

After having sketched a theoretical model about the remittance-backed securities to finance the public debt and after having stated that the research paradigm is post-positivism that relies mainly on quantitative methodology (time series and regressions) and on the analytic narrative to analyze the gathered time series data, I will try to answer the four hypotheses of this research which are:

- H₁: There is a need for Lebanon to obtain financing from international markets.
- H₂: There is a way to get financing through remittance-backed securities.
- H₃: There is a potential borrowing method from international markets using remittances inflows to Lebanon.
- H₄: There are benefits for Lebanon from borrowing throughout remittances backed securities.

This allows proving the problem statement through sketching a field model regarding the remittances-backed securities in financing the Lebanese public debt.

In order to do so and to test progressively the hypotheses, I will sketch the structure of the monetary system. Later, I will provide an overview of the Lebanese economy through narrating analytically how historically Lebanon dealt with its public debt and to determine the ways of financing the public debt. However, when addressing the public debt, this means also analyzing it. Finally, the remittances in Lebanon will be tackled. This will allow sketching the field model regarding the remittance-backed securities to finance the public debt of Lebanon.

The Structure of the Lebanese Monetary System

The Lebanese monetary system consists of the monetary system with the crucial role of Banque du Liban (BDL) or the Central Bank of Lebanon. It consists also of the credit rating, banking sector, securities markets, and treasury interest rates

Figure 25. The Lebanese monetary system structure.

Self-made figure based on the knowledge of this chapter.

Monetary System and Role of BDL

As Figure 25 showed, the single keeper of the Lebanese public funds is BDL. According to the Ministry of Finance, it regulates and oversees the banking system, has an authority to issue and look after the currency while enhancing monetary stability and promoting economic and social progress. As a matter of fact, since

Lebanon has a history of highly dollarized economy, stabilizing the Lebanese Pound (LBP) exchange rate while controlling the inflation rates and providing money growth has been the monetary policy of Lebanon since 1992. Thus, BDL pegged the Lebanese Pound to USD at a rate of LBP 1,507.5. Due to the policy of decreasing the dollarization of the economy, the foreign currency deposit proportion slowly decreased from 73.6% in 1990 to 65.7% in 2014 (Ministry of Finance, 2010).

Moreover, BDL advises the government in financial and economic matters. In addition, BDL has many other functions (see Figure 26).

Figure 26. BDL other functions.

Self-made figure based on Ministry of Finance (2010).

Treasury Interest Rates

Since the Lebanese currency is fixed, Lebanese interest rates follow U.S. interest rates. However, the Central bank retains the possibility of lowering interest rates by buying at a fixed rates government treasury bills and Eurobonds. Since the Central Bank is bearing the cost by buying treasury bills at lower rates, Lebanon pays lower interest rates than are suggested by credit rating authorities. In 2016, the

weighted interest rate of Treasury securities denominated in LBP varies from 4.39% for 3-month-treasury to 7.75% for 60-month-treasury (ABL, 2016).

Credit Rating

According to Standard and Poor's credit rating services, Lebanon had B-/B long and short-term foreign and local currency sovereign credit rating with a positive outlook in 2015. This rating was affirmed due to the several reasons. First, Lebanon historically has twin deficit in the fiscal and current accounts, existing political tension, and occasional absence of a president. However, decreasing oil prices will have favorable impact on the economy. Also, deposits inflows are expected to be high, enabling the Lebanon's banking sector to remain resilient and continue to finance the debt servicing. However, recently the rating was updated and currently Lebanon remained having B-/B rating but with negative outlook (Cullianan & Jelencovic, 2015).

Banking Sector

The Lebanese banking sector plays a very important role in the Lebanese economy. Being financially sound and stable, the banking industry dominates the financial system of the local economy. Due to its openness, substantial capitalization, and corporate governance, banks experienced resilience during the global financial crisis during 2007-2009. Being highly regulated and supervised, commercial banks are subject to the Code of Commerce (1942) and the Code of Money and Credit (1963). The banking system is regulated and supervised by the Bank du Liban (BDL) and Banking Control Commission (BCC) and works in cooperation with the Association of Banks in Lebanon (ABL). Also, banks are the major subscribers to the Lebanese treasury. Nearly 57 percent of the public debt is held by the commercial

banks. Over the past 50 years Lebanon had 60 to 92 banks of various sizes and types that are spread over 31 countries through branches, subsidiaries, affiliations, representative offices and sister companies (This Public Debt, 2014). In 2016 Lebanese banks are divided into several major categories such as commercial banks and investment banks.

Commercial banks include Lebanese banks S.A.L. (31 banks), Lebanese banks with Arab control S.A.L. (9 banks), Arab banks (7 banks), Foreign banks (4banks). The sector of the Investment Banks consists of 16 banks (ABL, 2016). The following Table 2 shows the development of the banking sector between 2005 and 2014.

Table 2

The Banking Sector Development

Year	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	<i>Change 2014/2015.%</i>
Bank Type. Number and Percent											
Commercial	54	54	54	53	53	54	54	54	56	55	1.9
Investment	10	9	12	12	12	13	15	17	17	16	37.5
<i>Banks Total</i>	<i>64</i>	<i>63</i>	<i>66</i>	<i>65</i>	<i>65</i>	<i>67</i>	<i>69</i>	<i>71</i>	<i>73</i>	<i>71</i>	<i>10.9</i>
Human resources. Number and Per cent											
Employees	15,993	16,538	17,664	18,632	19,794	21,337	21,881	22,637	23,136	23,850	49.1

Note. From the *Annual Reports of Association of Banks of Lebanon (2006-2014)*, retrieved from www.abl.org.lb

Since the main goal of the asset management plan is the adequate liquidity and earnings, Lebanese banks have limited investment opportunities. The Lebanese stock exchange is underdeveloped and the corporate bond market is not available. In addition, due to the conservative culture and policies of the local banks, investing

outside Lebanon is constrained by BDL. Thus, Lebanese commercial banks are able to invest in Treasury bills, Eurobonds, Certificates of Deposits (CDs) of the Central Banks and private sector loans (Ministry of Finance, 2010; The Lebanese Banking Sector, 2013).

Securities Markets

Being established in 1920, Beirut Stock Exchange (BSE) had an initial purpose of privatizing public companies. During the civil war BSE was closed and later reopened in 1996. Since that time several private companies have been added. Nowadays, only 11 companies are listed at BSE. In 2004, the Lebanese Eurobonds were listed on the Beirut Stock Exchange for the first time. The Government sees the Stock Exchange as an essential contributor to the country economic expansion and reconstruction. Thus, in 2011 Law 161 has been enacted in Lebanon. This law acts as a framework and governs all capital market activities in Lebanon, promoting trustworthiness and transparency. If developed to its full potential, the current stock exchange may act as a link between the Lebanese entrepreneurs and venture capitalists (Ministry of Finance, 2010).

After having dressed the structure of the Lebanese monetary system, I will move now to the development of the Lebanese economy and the public debt.

Development of the Lebanese Economy and the Public Debt

This section will address the development of the Lebanese economy prior to the 1975-1990 war, during the war, the 1990s, and early 2000s. The year 2006 which witnessed an Israeli aggression was a second inflexion point in the history of the Lebanese economy. Finally, the most recent period (2010-2016) of the economy will be studied. After each period, I will shed some light on the state of the public debt of

Lebanon. However, mentioning inflexion points leads to the use of the analytic narratives to tell the economic history of Lebanon, where an event occurs, disturbs the equilibrium of the Lebanese economy, and establish a new economic equilibrium (Bates et al., 1998). Figure 27 summarizes the economic history of Lebanon.

Figure 27. The analytic narratives of the Lebanese economy.

Self-made figure based on the knowledge of this chapter.

The Lebanese Economy Prior to Wars

Lebanon obtained its independence in 1943. Since that time it has followed a liberal economic system. This system provides freedom to private sector, including financial, economic and monetary aspects. In addition, currency transfers and external trade operations were free from restrictions. Due to this openness, Lebanon was able to attract foreign capital and investment from Arab and other countries, transforming the country into financial center. Regional trade allowed the Lebanese banks to grab a significant share from the revenue of the oil trading Arab countries.

The services sector expanded rapidly during the period of 1950-1960 due to the political development of the Arab countries and the finding of oil. The banking

sector outperformed the commodity sector (agriculture and industry) while accounting for nearly two-thirds of the total GDP, and number of banks increased from 23 to 93 banks. During that period Lebanon acted as an intermediary between Arab and advanced industrialized countries providing high annual economic growth of 5.6 percent of GDP during 1960-1973. The major contributors to that development were limited state intervention, monetary stability and floating exchange rate. However, the major weaknesses of the period were: inequality among the main economic sectors, problems in legislation and administration, vulnerability to external influences.

However, the period 1966-1975 changed the balance in the Lebanese economy. The collapse of Intra Bank in 1966 led to a decrease in the total number of operating banks, and the Arab-Israel War of 1967 led to the compression of the services sector. Meanwhile, industrial sector faced valuable expansion. Industrial investments and the share of manufactured products in total export increased considerably.

During the pre-Civil War period Lebanon experienced economic growth that allowed country to prosper; however, it also had several weaknesses that laid the base for the economic and political distortion and the civil war. Figure 28 summarizes both strength and weaknesses of the Lebanese economy during pre-war period.

The strengths mentioned above encouraged the period of rapid growth of the Lebanese economy during the 1960s and first half of 1970's. At the same time, weaknesses impacted, shaped and triggered the imbalance in the society that caused long and devastating civil war (United Nations development project, 1997).

Carolyn Gates mentioned two additional factors that contributed to the formation of the Lebanese society and its brake down after independence: - peripheral

capitalism (and its structure) and the issue of “who benefits?” from the development of Lebanon.

Figure 28. Strengths and weaknesses of the Lebanese economy (1943-1975).

Self-made figure based on the knowledge of this chapter.

Peripheral capitalism is related to the last quarter of the 19th century when European (mostly French) capitalists invested in the larger companies of the Levant. The European expansion encouraged the development of the Lebanese bourgeoisie who had to adhere to the European interests. Eventually, a model of “peripheral capitalist development emerged in Lebanon, which was characterized by extraversion (external orientation), dependence and underdevelopment” (Gates, 1989, p.8).

First, peripheral capitalism brought several issues:

- uneven development of agriculture
- weak industrialization process
- developed and dependent service sector
- imbalances in development of economic sectors

The results of this form of development were underemployment, inequalities, emigration and foreign dependence. Second, the “**who benefits?**” issue is related to the Western penetration and establishment of a weak state authority. Gates noted that this way of development benefited “mercantile-financial bourgeoisie” and a small “political-bureaucratic elite” that were allied with the West. At the same time, agrarian workers, rural landowners and craftsman (that accounted nearly to the half of population in 1960s) were suffering from this development mode. This system that had been established by western interests and the Lebanese power-bloc led to inequality and social turmoil that caused the most devastating period in the Lebanese history (Gates, 1989).

Evolution of the Lebanese Economy during and after the Wars

This section narrates the development of the Lebanese economy since 1975 and until now. It includes major events and economic indicators. The whole economic development is analyzed through a prism of the public debt. Thus, this part describes in details the Lebanese public debt, its change during time and the efforts that the government took in order to manage it.

Lebanese economy during 1975-1990. War in 1975, major Israeli invasions in 1978 and in 1982, Iraqi invasion of Kuwait in 1990, and domestic violence – all these events interrupted the course of development. Lebanon was affected in several ways. Figure 29 summarizes them.

Figure 29. Economic development of Lebanon (1975 -1990).

Self-made figure based on United Nations development project (1997).

Public Debt. The loss of the government ability to collect revenues led to a severe increase in budget deficit of 91.1% in 1984. By 1991 the public debt had reached 50% of GDP. In order to finance budget deficit, the Lebanese government issued LBP denominated treasury bills with high interest rates of 25 percent and 35 percent in 1987 and 1992, respectively. The main holders of the bills were commercial banks and the Central Bank of Lebanon. Eventually, this led to increasing the money supply, growing inflation rates and a deteriorating exchange rate. Growth of internal debt was the main feature of the Lebanese economy during years of war, where the loss of government revenues and increase in defense expenditures were its main contributors.

The balance of payment was also severely affected during war. Since Lebanon has always been an importing country, its trade deficit has been balanced by services

and a capital account surplus. Decrease in exports and capital inflows due to decline in remittances from the Gulf countries widened the balance of payment deficit. In 1990, trade deficit was recorded at \$ 1,802 million (United Nations development project, 1997).

The Lebanese economy during 1990s. After fifteen years of war, the post-war reconstruction and stabilization of the economy were the major goals of the Lebanese government. Besides the human casualties, damage to physical assets that amounted 25 billion USD, displacement of 20% of the educated and skilled workers, and weakening of the public institutions were the major destructive results of the devastating civil war (Ministry of Finance, 2003).

When the war ended, Lebanon faced several global economic developments, the major one being significant progress in technology and communication, increasing levels of free international trade with lower tariffs and barriers, shifts to more liberal policies in advanced economies that decreased the economic role of state, and the growth of indebtedness in developing countries. The process of the recovery of the Lebanese economy could not neglect such regional and global realities. Thus, the recovery had to take into consideration new international mechanisms to establish effective governing that would encourage the country's development and attract international capital and investment.

In 1989, a national reconciliation pact, called the Taif Accord, was signed. This agreement, negotiated in Taif, Saudi Arabia, ended the Lebanese civil war (Krayem, n.d). In the early 1990s Lebanon faced a recovery period characterized by the growth of GDP, declining inflation, and a surplus in balance of payments. Improvement of the public finance, revenue collection and expenditure restraints led to overall reduction of the deficit. Elections of the parliament in 1992 led to the

government formation. The new Prime Minister, Rafic Hariri, stimulated a new wave of stability, both political and economic.

After mid-1992 the major goal of the government of this period was the establishment of the economic stability. The medium-term policy was control over the budget deficit and its gradual reduction. The goal was to achieve this by revenue increases through tax system reforms and expenditure rationalization. Thus, the first half of 1990s enjoyed a remarkable economic recovery with the average growth of GDP by 7 percent (1993-1995), declining inflation from 120 in 1992 to a single-digit number in 1996, increased foreign exchange reserves and the strong growth of commercial banks assets. However, success at the macro-level had its costs. High treasury bills rates, increased level of required reserves and restructuring of deposits and lending operations of the Lebanese banks caused liquidity problems.

Public Debt. Public debt grew fast during first half of 1990s. Also, despite the fact that the trade deficit dropped to 10% in 1995, internal and external public debt continued its rapid growth due to financial needs for the recovery, reconstruction and development of the Lebanese economy. During that period, the public debt was recorded as short term domestic debt with high interest rate of 35 percent in 1992 and about 15 percent in 1995. About 60 percent of the treasury bills were obligatory held by commercial banks. Even though high amount of foreign reserves allows Lebanon to borrow externally, in 1995, the share of external debt recorded only at 15% of the total debt (Ministry of Finance, 2003).

In response, the government attempted to change the composition of the debt, to reduce the interest rates and to decrease the debt holding share of the Lebanese banks to 40 percent.

Due to several elements of strength in the economy, such as openness of the economic system, favorable environment to private investment and leading role of service-producing sectors, the Lebanese government was able to focus on “ promoting confidence in the economy, and attempting to achieve the dual objective of economic stabilization – especially cutting the budget deficit and absorbing the internal debt - rebuilding and rehabilitation the physical, social and institutional infrastructure” (United Nations development project, 1997, p14).

In 1992, the Lebanese government adopted the National Emergency Rehabilitation Program (NERP) that in 1994 changed in to a ten-year plan called Horizon 2000 for Development and Reconstruction, announced. The main objectives of the plan were reestablishment of infrastructure, fair regional distribution of public investment, and encouragement of private sector development through savings. The plan was very ambitious, not specific and challenging bearing in mind the fiscal deficit and debt (United Nations development project, 1997; Lebanon: Paris II, 2002). External support was provided only in the form of loans from GCC funds and countries, EU institutions and the World Bank. However, the Lebanese institutions had difficulty complying with requirements associated with the loans. In addition, Lebanon had a limited ability to access medium-term external loans during early 1990s. Moreover, due to difficulty in accessing international capital market and the Asian financial crisis, Lebanon turned to borrowing US dollars domestically (Lebanon: Paris II, 2002).

Major highlights of the development of the Lebanese economy during described period are depicted in Figure 30.

Figure 30. Economic development of Lebanon during 1990s.

Self-made figure based on United Nations development project (1997), Ministry of Finance (2003).

The Lebanese economy during early 2000s. Eventually, the Lebanese government asked the President of France to consider a request for support of Lebanon through members of the Paris Club. The Lebanese government approached Paris II with the following. Due to unbearable interest payments on public debt that amounted US\$30 billion and engrossed nearly 80% of the revenue, government did not request support through grants and soft loans, but rather assistance in the changing the whole composition of debt. The government attempted to reduce the debt cost and to lengthen the maturity of the current debt through the following. The Lebanese government requested US \$5 billion loan with the payback period of 10 years. During that time, the government expected to generate fiscal surpluses and decrease interest rates to around 4%. According to the Law No. 430, a special treasury account was

established within the Central Bank for the purpose of serving the principal and interests of the outstanding debt. As a result of the Paris II conference, Lebanon was promised \$4.4 billion from several countries and financial institutions. The management of the debt reduction was projected to consume \$3.1 billion while the remaining amount had to be use for development projects financing (Lebanon: Paris II, 2002; Ministry of Finance, 2003).

However, to win support from President Chirac, the EU, the World Bank and the Vice-President of the European Investment Bank (EIB), the Government program of 2002-2004 needed to be implemented. The Lebanese government had several challenges, such as the need of fiscal adjustments and the debt reduction, that were attempted to be reached by promotion of the BOP surplus, privatization and stimulation of the economic growth (Lebanon: Paris II, 2002).

The major contributor to revenue increase was the introduction of the Value Added Tax (VAT) in 2002. VAT represented 10% addition to the price of goods and services. Also, strengthening the tax administration, restructuring of several public sector companies, and a new public accounting law also played an important role in the public debt reduction (VAT, 2001).

Eventually, in 2003 the commitment was fulfilled and the Lebanese government received the amount pledged during the Paris II. Proceeds were resulted to several 15-year USD denominated 5 percent Eurobond issues that were subscribed by donor countries, such as Malaysia, Kuwait, United Arab Emirates, Oman, Saudi Arabia and Qatar. As a result, the Lebanon's public debt, both foreign and domestic, was retired and replaced.

Specially, as a result of previously discussed actions, US\$2,700 billion of the 24-month LBP denominated Treasury bill portfolio was retired and the remaining

US\$1,221 billion Eurobond portfolio was exchanged into a new, 1.87 billion of dollar denominated 15-year, 4% Eurobond with a 5-year grace period for principal. This transaction decreased the total public debt nearly by 10 percent of GDP. Also, it saved around USD 350 million in debt services.

In addition, according to the decision #8312, in order to reduce debt, BDL obliged all banks that operate in Lebanon to subscribe to the Lebanese no-interest, 2-year Treasury bills and Eurobonds. The amount had to be equivalent to 10 percent of the total bank's deposits. According to this scheme, commercial banks contributed USD 1,784 billion in 2003 which were deposited in the special account at BDL and have been used only for public debt management purposes (Lebanon: Paris II, 2013).

As a result, nearly 24 percent of the most expensive, short-term public debt was replaced, thus decreasing the cost of financing by about 3 percent. Total public debt decreased from 11.9% of GDP in 2002 to 9.8% in 2003 (Lebanon: Paris II, 2013). The result of these transactions and the change in cost of debt is summarized in Table 3.

Table 3

Treasury Bill Yields (Primary Market)

	Pre-Paris II	Post-Paris II
3-months T-bills	11.18%	6.96%
6-months T-bills	12.12%	8.18%
12-months T-bills	13.43%	9.13%
24-months T-bills	16.64%	9.20%

Note. Data for Treasury bill yields reprinted from *Lebanon: Paris II Meeting*, 2003, p. 7, retrieved from www.hariri-foundation.org.

As shown in the Table 3, Paris II transaction had favorable impact on interest rates. Also, Lebanon experienced improvements in its balance of payments, a decrease in dollarization, and declines of short-term and overnight borrowing rates. In order to farther reduce its deficits, the Lebanese government enacted several fiscal reforms, such as 5 percent tax on interest, increased prices of fixed line call fees and subscriptions together with additional reforms that were introduced by Ministry of Finance (See Figure 31) (Lebanon: Paris II, 2003).

During 2004, all of the efforts led to the strong economic performance, a decrease of interest payments, nearly 7% growth of GDP, and a decline of budget deficit. However, the assassination of the Prime Minister Hariri in 2005 and rising oil prices stopped the upward trend of the development of Lebanon. Despite the economic challenges, new Prime Minister Siniora attempted to rejuvenate the whole economy, leading to improvements of economic indicators during mid-2005 and June 2006.

Figure 31. Paris II meeting results (2002).

Self-made figure based on the knowledge of this chapter.

Lebanese economy after the Israeli war 2006. Prior the Israeli war in July, 2006, Lebanon was on its way to a fruitful touristic season. Moreover, Siniora's government paved the way for series of reforms including growth, financial and capital markets, public finance and debt management. However, the Israeli war had a devastating effect on the reform plans and the whole Lebanese economy. "Attacks by land, sea and air resulted in tragic loss of human life, large-scale displacement and massive damage to private and public infrastructure, and a complete dislocation of the economy" (Lebanese Republic, 2007, p.5). As a result, Lebanon deviated from the course of the near bright future and the economic sustainability. The total cost of reconstruction was estimated at nearly US\$2.8 billion (Lebanese Republic, 2007).

Public Debt. The Lebanese fiscal situation suffered a severe impact due to the war. The economy experienced increase in the gross public debt totaling nearly US\$ 40 billion or 180% of GDP (Lebanese Republic, 2007). Large short term obligations, revenue loss that led to the fiscal deficit and the need for reconstruction (estimated at nearly US\$1.75 billion) were among the public debt contributors after the war (Lebanese Republic, 2007).

Due to the international community's generous support, a Conference for Early Recovery took place in Stockholm where Lebanon received financial contributions totaling US\$ 900 million from several Arab and European countries. In order to maintain transparency of the funds' use, special accounts with BDL have been opened for every donor.

Despite the consequences of the civil war and as a result external financing needs, the Lebanese government had always met its debt obligation, even during the war. However, after the 2006 war, reducing the ratio of current expenditure to GDP became very complicated. Thus, since the large public debt is the main source of

economic vulnerability, taking all possible measure to place the debt on descending trend became a major goal of the Lebanese economy during following years. In order to achieve economic sustainability, the Lebanese government prepared and presented a complex of reforms that would boost economic growth, create employment, maintain social and public stability, and move a country to prosperity. However, due to post-war increase in the public debt burden, Lebanon will not be able to meet any of the goals mentioned without significant external support. Thus, the Lebanese authorities again requested help of the international community.

In 2007, 36 countries and 14 multinational institutions attended the International Conference for Support to Lebanon, the Paris III Conference. As a result of this meeting, Lebanon had received nearly US \$ 1.3 billion loans and grants. In addition, IMF granted Lebanon US\$37 million as Emergency Post-Conflict Assistance (Ministry of Finance, 2010). Public debt during post-war period due to international assistance was decreasing from 167 percent in 2006 to 156 percent and 139 percent in 2008 and 2009, respectively. More detailed information about the public debt during 2000s in terms of types of creditors and currency is available in Appendix II (Ministry of Finance, 2010, pp. 60-63).

Years (2007-2009) that followed the Israeli war characterized by minor political problems, an increase in the minimum wage from LL 300,000 to LL 500,000 per month, election of the new president Michel Sleiman (2008) and new government formation in 2009. Real GDP growth was at 7.5 and 9.3 percent in 2007 and 2008, respectively, with market services and trade sectors as major contributors. Despite the trade deficit, the balance of payments recorded a surplus in 2007 and 2008 due to increase in the financial and capital accounts (see Figure 32). All of these enhanced economic stability and improved confidence in Lebanon (Ministry of Finance, 2010).

Figure 32. Economic development of Lebanon (2000-2009).

Self-made figure based on Lebanese Republic (2007), Ministry of Finance (2010).

The Lebanese economy: recent years (2010-2016). The period of time from 2010 and until today has been characterized by sluggish performance of the economy with the main goals of decreasing the public debt, increasing growth and attaining stability.

Due to the war in Syria, Lebanon became a home for nearly two millions of Syrian refugees. International agencies provided help for hosting community; however, more is urgently needed. Refugee crisis pressures Lebanese public financing and already suffering infrastructure. As unemployment doubled and reached 20% and poverty is increasing, reaching the projected GDP growth rate of 4 - 4.5 percent was extremely hard. Thus, in 2011 GDP growth rate decreased to 2-3 percent which was far less than projected. Real estate, construction and tourism, that used to be major

contributor to growth in Lebanon, faced significant downturns during discussing period.

Resilience of the foreign-exchange and financial markets and large non-resident deposit inflows have contributed to the growth. However, the presidential vacuum since min-2014, the garbage crisis and public demonstrations on the streets of Beirut undermined confidence of the Lebanese political system. The country often moves backward proving that the will of politicians to cooperate and work on the current situation towards the common good is diminishing.

In order to secure economic sustainability and growth, Lebanon is in need of policies that will move the country forward. The IMF advises implement of several steps in order to secure fiscal balance and space for social projects and spending:

- Salary adjustments for public sectors,
- Increase fuel taxation and broader tax bases
- Implement the electricity improvements
- Strengthen bank supervision
- Privatize the Beirut Stock Exchange

Taking into consideration the previous suggestion, IMF estimated increase in *real GDP* growth to 3 percent in 2017 and reaching 4 percent starting 2019. *Inflation* is estimated to be set around 2 percent during 2016-20 from 2016 onward (Audi Bank, 2015; International Monetary Fund, 2015).

According to the annual report of Audi bank, there are several means to overcome the sluggish performance of the Lebanese economy that includes:

- Stimulation of private investments, leading to an increase in private consumption and the creation of job opportunities.
- Decrease trade deficit through import substitution and export oriented products (\$1.5 billion trade deficit on average over the past 4 years)

- Infrastructure upgrade. Transport, water, energy and telecommunication sectors of the Lebanese economy need an upgrade. Over the past five years, government spent only nearly 1% of GDP on public investments in infrastructure.
- Mitigation of fiscal drift. With its high debt to GDP ratio of 134% in 2014, Lebanon is the third most indebted worldwide compared to its peer countries in the emerging markets with the average debt ratio of 34% (Audi Bank, 2015).

As we may see, high public debt is one of the major reasons that constantly drag the Lebanese economy backwards.

Lebanese Debt Structure and Trends

Nowadays, Lebanon has one of the highest debt-to-GDP ratios in the world. According to Blominvest Bank research, the sustainability of the Lebanese debt is not always an attribute of the reduction of the ratio, but is the result of sound policy action and reforms navigation.

Historically, the public debt development has generally had an upward trend. Figure 33 depicts the changes over time in the debt-to-GDP ratio. In 2014, public debt denominated in USD was 57.1 percent to GDP while Lebanese pounds denominated debt was 81.2 percent to GDP; thus, accounting nearly at 140 percent to GDP in total. The cost of debt was 5.9 percent on foreign debt and 6.7 percent on the local currency debt. According to the Association of Banks in Lebanon' report, most of the debt is financed by the local commercial banks. In addition, nearly 40% of the total portion carried by the banks is denominated in US dollars (see Figure 34).

*Figure 33.*Debt-to-GDP ratio of Lebanon.

Reprinted from Debt Sustainability Analysis for Lebanon 2015-2020, p. 2, by Daou & Mikhael, 2015, from <http://blog.blominvestbank.com/>

The Central Bank of Lebanon holds a considerable portion of the debt, 20%. Public institutions such as National Security Fund and National Guarantee Institutions hold 7.5% of the debt while the non-bank private sector in Lebanon holds only 6% of the total debt. Finally, only small portion of the public debt is carried by the foreign investors and related to the debt swap procedure that was discussed earlier in this chapter. The portfolio of public debt of Lebanon is comprised of government bills, bonds and loans. Also, interest over public debt consumes nearly 40 percent of the total government revenues; thus, the Lebanese government development expenditures are limited (This Public Debt, 2014).

Figure 34. Performance of Lebanon and public debt (2010-2016).

Self-made figure based on Audi Bank (2015), International Monetary Fund (2015), This Public Debt (2014).

Economic development and public debt forecasts. Blominvest bank

researchers Daou and Mikhael (2015) suggests two scenarios of the Lebanese debt development. *Best case scenario* states that Lebanon will be able to decrease the ratio to 135% by 2020 if the country will be able to stabilize real GDP growth at 3.5%, to increase the government revenues to 23% of GDP and decrease the government expenditures to 29% of GDP and will maintain the indicators at the suggested levels for the period 2016-2020.

The worst case scenario assumes, that the real GDP growth will remain at 2% maximum with increase in the government expenditures due to a \$1.2B salary scale increase for the public employees with no additional revenue measures. Those steps will deteriorate the fiscal and the primary balance thus leading to unsustainable

development of the public debt and an increase in debt-to-GDP ratio to 179% in 2020. This increase in ratio will inevitably lead to the sovereign downgrade of Lebanon (Daou & Mikhael, 2015).

Regardless of any scenario that takes place in the near future, the public debt will still be considered high. As a result, Lebanon will have to keep financing its public debt at higher interest rates. In order to understand the suggestion of the Lebanese authorities regarding the debt-management techniques, we will take a look at the *Debt Management Strategy 2014-2016* issued by Ministry of Finance of Lebanon. Also we will analyze the opinions of the international institutions and rating agencies.

According to the Ministry of Finance (2014), besides the high level of the public debt, Lebanon faces several additional issues related to the debt financing. First, since the debt almost solely held by the domestic market, increasing amount of debt faces an issue of the limited absorptive capacity. In addition, according to the Lebanese Ministry of Finance, “domestic financing capacity has shown to be a potential bottleneck”. A second issue is related to the high expense of the debt financing. Currently, the interest on debt consumes 40 percent of the total government revenues. Thus, the medium term debt management strategy is based on several aspects, such as

- Increased reliance on foreign borrowing for covering redemptions and interest payments of foreign currency debt
- Extension of maturities beyond the current level of 4.3 years (Ministry of Finance, 2014)

In addition, Standard & Poor’s rating agency, that regularly issues sovereign credit ratings, stated such a high concentration of government financing in the

banking system “as a structural weakness that leaves Lebanon more vulnerable to adverse business, financial, and economic conditions” (Cullinan & Jelenkovic, 2015. p.4). The authors also mention that S&P’s considers raising the rating of Lebanon in case the public finances would become more sustainable.

Public Debt Analysis

Debt Growth Analysis

In order to finalize the discovered results related to the public debt in Lebanon, this section of the research will provide the analysis of the public debt discussed in the chapter 3. The primary interest of this part is to analyze the growth of the public debt of Lebanon based on available data. I will take a look at the growth of debt from the perspective of major events that took place in Lebanon for the past 20 years. The analysis will cover the period from 1994 until 2015 due to availability of the data related to the public debt (see Figure 35).

Figure 35. Annual growth rate of public debt of Lebanon (percent).

Self-made figure based on Mottu & Nakhle (2011), BDL (2016).

Generally, the public debt of Lebanon is constantly increasing (due to many reasons described in chapter 4) but at a decreasing rate. That shows when we compare the debt growth in 1994 (60 percent), 1999 (17 percent), 2004 (6.7 percent) and 2010 (6.3 percent). As analysis revealed, since 2007 and until 2011 the growth of the public debt was increasing at a decreasing rate and reached 3 percent growth. The growth of the debt is significantly decreasing during the period of international assistance in debt reduction. However, starting from 2012 the debt began to grow again. According to the analysis, for the period from 2012 and until 2014 the growth level of debt is stabilized at nearly 8 percent growth per year.

Debt-to-GDP Ratio Analysis

Debt-to-GDP ratio is one of the ratios that are considered while analyzing the public debt. As this ratio determines indebtedness of the country and its ability to pay its dues, analysis of this ratio has been performed. In order to calculate the ratio, I used available BDL figures of GDP for the period 1993-2015. From the debt part I used Net Total Debt figures for the same time period. I did not use Gross Public Debt figures since it includes the portion of the total debt that government owes to itself and it is not a burden to the economy. Rather I took a look at the growth of debt that is held by the public, which is recorded as a net total debt and represents a burden to the economy. Figure 36 presents the results.

As the figure shows, Net Total Debt-to-GDP ratio follows an upward trend increasing from nearly 40% in 1993 to 120% in 2015. The growth of the ratio was the most significant during 1990s. The GDP growth was high averaging 13 % per year as a result of heavy government investment for reconstruction and infrastructure that was damaged during the long civil war. Sometimes growth of the public debt reached 60 percent. During the early 2000s the ratio began to stabilize due to government efforts

and international assistance of Paris II (2002). Starting 2006 the ratio began to dive reaching its past 10 years' minimum of 113.7% in 2013. For the past two years, the ratio is back to its upward trend.

Figure 36. Net total debt-to-GDP (billion, USD, percent).

Self-made figure based on BDL (2016), Lebanon GDP (2016).

In addition, according SPSS results regarding the linear regression between the public debt and GDP, there is a coefficient of correlation $r = 0.944$, thus

$$\text{Public debt} = Y = 1.250 \text{ GDP} + 0.190$$

This means that there is a positive correlation between the debt and GDP. Thus, if GDP will keep increasing, the net total public debt will keep increasing.

Based on the all of the previously discussed information we may answer the first research question: *Is there a need to get financing from international market?* As we learned from our research so far the public debt problem has been a continuous issue to Lebanon. Since its independence the country has faced several challenges in maintaining a sustainable level of the public debt. Not only is the increasing growth of the debt challenging for Lebanon but also the limited absorption capacity of the local market to hold the debt presents difficulties. Since the amount of the debt increases over time (as the linear regression proves) while the Lebanese market size remains considerably stable, it will be challenging for the long term to fully finance the public debt from the local market. The Ministry of Finance considers this situation as potential bottle neck while for credit rating agencies it weakens the Lebanese local environment. Taking into consideration the growth rate of the debt, we believe that Lebanon eventually will exhaust possibility of borrowing only from the local market. Thus, the country should consider a possibility of borrowing internationally. This also would be challenging having a speculative sovereign rating of B-/B. However, the following part of this chapter would demonstrate that this is possible and even beneficial particularly by answering the second research question: *Is there a way to get financing through remittance-backed securities?* Later the chapter will find out the answer on the third research question: *How to borrow from international markets using remittances inflows to Lebanon?* Finally, the chapter will end by determining benefits of the securitization to Lebanon.

Remittances in Lebanon

Remittances and Migration in Lebanon: Importance and Characteristics

Remittances are projected future flows of emigrants' money into Lebanon. In order to use them as underlying assets they should be stable or even countercyclical

inflows of hard currency. We will answer our second research question by analyzing trends of remittances flows to Lebanon.

Lebanon is continuously migrating country with a globally dispersed diaspora all over the world estimated at nearly four times as large as country's population or up to 14 million people (Jamali & Lanteri, 2015). Due to the main reason of migration – unemployment – Lebanese were constantly migrating since the state's independence in 1943 and until modern days. The continuous migration of skillful workers is considered a “brain drain” and negatively affects migrating country. However, at the same time it represents a huge potential. Lebanese migrants maintain very close relations with their family members in Lebanon. Expatriates help their home country in several ways. They send money transfers, create businesses and trades, and build hospitals, school and churches. In addition, they sponsor organizations that solve social problems in Lebanese villages and towns (Hourani, 2007). Finally, since remittances in Lebanon are mostly used for household consumption, such as daily expenses, healthcare, education and housing, remittances influx acts like a shaping instrument for Lebanon's middle class (Jamali & Lanteri, 2015).

Historically, remittances have been major contributors of a capital to the Lebanese banking sector. They decrease current account deficit of Lebanon. Wazne mentions that remittances are “the backbone of the Lebanese economic and financial system”. He also states that sustainability of the Lebanese government funding model will be problematic without remittances since they finance government needs and the private sector borrowing once they have entered the banking system (Wazne, n.d.). In addition, the Lebanese government was able to raise essential funds in 1991 through Diaspora bonds. The money was used for reduction of the amount of the public debt (Hourani, 2007).

A large global network of the Lebanese banking sector is spread all over more than 30 countries in five continents. Most of the Lebanese banks abroad are registered as subsidiaries, branches or representative offices. The majority of them provide “expatriate banking services” thus encouraging official money transfers to the home country.

According to the World Bank, in 2014 Lebanon was the 14th largest remittance-recipient in the world and the 2nd largest remittance-recipient among Arab countries, following Egypt. Remittances to Lebanon are equal to 1.5% of global remittances inflow. Also, remittances are measured at 17.8% to GDP which is 11th highest such ratio in the world (World Bank, 2014). In addition, in 2003 Lebanon received \$2.7 billion US dollars that ranked Lebanon number one in the world in terms of remittances per capita (\$575 per capita) (Hourani, 2007).

Nowadays, majority of the Lebanese emigrants are educated or skilled workers. According to electronic cash transfers information in Lebanon, in 2014 majority of cash transfers came from Arab countries, around 50% (UAE-24%, Saudi Arabia, Qatar, Kuwait), while less than 20% came from Americas, Australia and Canada. The remaining amount used to come from Africa and Europe (Awdeh, 2014; The Lebanese Banking Sector, 2013). According to the remittances data report from the World Bank (2016), the amount of remittances into Lebanon was recorded at US\$7.163 billion. This number includes the total amount of remittances. The major senders of remittances in 2016 were United States, Australia, Canada, and the Gulf countries. However, the main portion of money transfers came from US, Canada and Australia (nearly 40%) while Arab countries’ residents sent only around 25% of the total remittances (World Bank, 2016). Decreasing amount of inflows from Gulf countries is related to the decreased oil price. In addition, political escalation between

Sunni and Shia Muslims forced many Lebanese to leave United Arab Emirates thus decreasing the amount of remittances.

Worldwide edging up of remittances in developing countries in 2015 took place also due to the decreased oil prices that affected the earnings of international emigrants and their ability to send money home. In 2015 total remittances grew only by 0.4 % and recorded as US\$ 431.3 billion compared to US\$ 430 billion in 2014. In Middle East and North Africa region remittances recorded a decrease of 0.9% mainly due to the decrease in inflows to Egypt. However, they are expected to grow in 2016 by 2.6% and reach US\$ 50.3 billion (World Bank, 2016).

Although Lebanon is one of the major remittances recipients in MENA, they have limited impact on the job creation and economic growth. Thus, Lebanese authorities haven't managed to benefit from remittances inflows to promote sustainable and long-term growth. According to the Awdeh (2014) research, remittances in Lebanon have the smallest correlation coefficient of 0.07 with the growth rate. They also have a negative correlation coefficient with current account and budget deficit, (0.58) and (0.19) respectively (Awdeh, 2014). In addition, according to Nassib Ghobril, chief economist at the Byblos Bank Group, despite the fact that expatriates send their remittances back home

“at a stable and steady pace...there is no vision or concrete strategy in place to maintain and strengthen the links between the Lebanese diaspora and Lebanon, especially that the general approach towards Lebanese expatriates consists of treating them like a bank account” (World Bank: Remittances to Lebanon, 2016).

This shows that remittance inflows create the potential for the receiving country that is underused by the government authorities. Figure 37 summarizes all mentioned above.

Figure 37. Remittances in Lebanon.

Self-made figure based on Wazne (n.d.), Hourani (2007), World Bank (2014), Awdeh (2014).

Stability of Remittance Inflows during Crises

Capital inflows typically have positive effects on any economy. Compared to FDI that falls during unfavorable periods, remittances are stable and counter-cyclical in response to political or economic downturns and even natural disasters. According to Byblos Bank (2011), remittances inflows did not decrease significantly during the global financial crisis 2007-2009. The research suggested that this situation took place due to the following factors:

- Lack of exchange rate effects (Lebanese currency is pegged to the US dollar)
- Absence of mass return migration
- Increase of economic risks in GCC countries (Byblos Bank, 2011)

Moreover, increases in the levels of political and economic risks in Lebanon leads to the increase in remittances flows. Pattern of remittances inflow has “and increasing trend but inconsistent growth rate” (Byblos Bank, 2011).

Remittances analysis. Based on Balance of Payment data retrieved from the Central Bank of Lebanon (BDL), I constituted analysis of remittances inflows and outflows in order to determine pattern, trends and to forecast their future movements. First, I found out total amount of recorded remittances for the time period 2002-2014 together with their monthly totals and monthly averages. Then, time series of net remittance flows (inflows minus outflows), linear trends and forecasts were performed regarding the amount of remittances in 2015 (detailed calculations are available in Appendix II). Figure 38 represents the results

Generally, during the early 2000s remittances experienced an upward trend and significant increases. Then, in 2005 they slightly decreased but picked up the upward trend during the two following years facing the Israeli war and as a result recovery. Later, 2008 through 2012 remittances experiences a period of a constant decrease that was ended in 2013. As time series and forecast showed, remittances back to their growth from 2013 and until now.

Data analysis produced several results:

- Remittances in Lebanon have an *upward trend*. During the discussed period (2002 – 2014) recorded remittances increased by nearly 4000 percent from USD34.7 million to USD 1.4 billion.
- Remittances are *countercyclical*. Despite the fact that remittances decreased by nearly 40 percent in 2005, they significantly increased in 2006 when Israeli war took place in Lebanon. The will of Lebanese migrants to support their family members during turbulent events in their home countries explains the counter-cyclicity of remittances. In addition, even though Lebanon was not significantly affected by the Global Financial Crisis due to the sound banking system the countries where remittances come from were. Thus, remittances

faced downward trend from 2008 and until 2012. However, even during that time they remain a positive figure due to wide geographical distribution of Lebanese migrants around the world.

- Remittances are stable. The study revealed that amount of remittance remains positive number despite the local economic and political events.

Figure 38. Net remittances in Lebanon (billion, USD).

Self-made figure, data for remittances from BDL (2017).

As we may notice that Lebanese emigrants increased their support during turbulent times. That is supported by the fact that the amount of remittances increased during the July 2006 Israeli war. In addition, it didn't significantly dropped during the Global Financial Crisis of 2009.

As study of Ghobril (2012) revealed, Lebanon is among the smallest of MENA region countries however one of the largest recipients of remittances. The author analyzed remittance trends in Lebanon and the effect of the global financial crisis. He also determined the economic impact of those trends. Ghobril concluded that the size of the Lebanese emigrant stock as well as several domestic and external factors contributed to the increasing remittances inflows to Lebanon. Also, the global financial crisis did not have negative impact on the remittances inflow. The major contributor to this stability appears to be the continuous migration from Lebanon. Thus, the negative effects of the financial crisis were “offset by the large stock of migrants, their income level, the lack of exchange rate effects, and no mass return migration” (Ghobril, 2012, p.376).

We may conclude by citing Dr. Guita Hourany, the director of the Lebanese Emigration Research Center (LERC) and the Campaign Coordinator for “Lebanon: Land of Dialogue among Civilizations and Cultures” Initiative at Notre Dame University (NDU):

The Lebanese Diaspora’s “memory and vision of the homeland [and] commitment to restoring Lebanon to its old glory has driven them to maintain and nurture a continuing relationship with homeland” (Hourani, 2007).

The previous part of the study revealed the fact that the pattern of the remittances inflow to Lebanon (which is stable and countercyclical) is suitable for its use as underlying assets for remittance-backed securities. In order to understand technical parts related to remittances securitization we will create a model of how Lebanon may get engaged in issuance of RBSs. This part provides the answer to the following research question: *How to borrow from international markets using remittances inflows to Lebanon?*

Borrowing Internationally through Remittances: Mode I

In order to answer the following research question, we will consider the example of Banco do Brasil described in the Chapter 2 and draw a model of how Lebanon could issue remittance-backed securities. In order to do so we have to choose the remitting country with the highest amount of remittances in order to issue securities for the largest possible amount. Let us consider that Lebanon would like to securitize remittances inflows that are coming from the most substantial contributor of remittances to the country. For example, Lebanon may choose among the major contributors of remittances, Saudi Arabia or United states. Table 4 summarizes unilateral remittances flows from these countries to Lebanon for the past six years.

Table 4

Remittances Estimate (Millions of USD)

Year	USA	Saudi Arabia
2010	1,578	640
2011	1,551	632
2012	1,538	627
2013	1,259	1,594
2014	1,195	1,505
2015	1,149	1,447

Note. Self-made table based on Bilateral Remittances (2014).

We may notice from the table that remittance inflows from USA facing decreasing trend while remittance inflows from Saudi Arabia have positive and cyclical trends. This takes place due to the negative effect of the global financial crisis and the low oil prices in the economies of the sending countries. However, it will not

severely affect the Lebanese securitization deal which will be limited to the amount of 10 percent of the total inflows having a required overcollateralization ratio.

Next step for Lebanon is to assign the branch or a representative office of a Lebanese bank that operates in the sending country (USA or Saudi Arabia) and initiates the official flow of remittances to Lebanon through that bank and its branches. The borrowing entity (for example, Banque du Liban) has to pledge the future receivables from Saudi Arabia or USA to Special Purpose Vehicle (SPV) that is located offshore. SPV will issue debt securities (bonds) that would be sold to the investors. BDL also should have a trustee that would make principal and interest payments to the investors and send excess collection of receivables to the BDL. Then, the designated correspondent bank will have to channel all remittances of the borrowing bank to the offshore collection account that is managed by the trustee.

The described structure requires official rating from the rating agency. As we mentioned the rating is usually higher than the sovereign rating since it takes place offshore. Similar to the BdB securitization deal that was graded BBB+ against its sovereign rating of BB - (which is five notches above the sovereign rating), Lebanon may potentially obtain an investment grade of BBB- instead of its current highly speculative rating of B-/B.

Also, the advice and guidance from the World Bank and IMF is required to establish the structure. Usually, the advisors from WB or IMF help developing countries with such securitization deals. They participate in creations of the whole structure including estimation of the possible borrowing amount and determination of basic securitization participants. The following model depicted in Figure 39 sketches the possible securitization of remittance-backed security deals.

Figure 39. A model of remittance securitization of Lebanon.

Self-made figure based on the knowledge of this chapter and chapter 2.

As we shall note, the structure does not retain remittances abroad, it only wires them through its participants. Remittances reach their final destination fully and in time so receiving parties are not affected by this deal.

Benefits and Obstacles of Remittance-backed Securities

This final part of the chapter 4 will answer the last research question: *What are the benefits to Lebanon from borrowing through remittance-backed securities?* Borrowing through remittances backed securities, Lebanon will benefit from all major benefits similar to other developing countries that use this structure to obtain financing (see Figure 40).

Benefits		Obstacles
<p><u>International fund access</u></p> <p>Remittance-backed security deal rating BBB- against sovereign B-/B rating</p>	<p><u>Lower cost of debt</u></p> <p>Up to 700 basis points savings)</p>	<p>High cost (up to US\$ 2 million)</p> <p>Time consuming</p> <p>Improvement of the legal framework could be challenging during current political situation</p>
<p><u>Extension of maturities</u></p> <p>The investment grade of RBSs enable larger specter of investors to buy such a security and hold it until maturity</p>	<p><u>External benefits</u></p> <p>-Legal framework improvement -Closer relationships with diaspora -Possible decrease of remittances transfer costs</p>	

Figure 40. Benefits and obstacles of remittances securitization in Lebanon.

Self-made figure based on the knowledge of this chapter.

International funds access. First benefit is the access to the international market. Currently, Lebanon's sovereign rating is B - /B with a negative outlook with a potential of downgrading in the future. This grade is considered speculative according to the major credit rating agencies thus restraining Lebanon from borrowing in international markets. As discussed in chapter 2, the securitization involving remittances due to its structure is usually rated up to five notches above the sovereign rating. If Lebanon would issue RBSs, the rating of the deal would be BBB - compared to the sovereign rating of B-/B. Thus, high rating allows Lebanon to access international markets.

Lower cost of debt. Second benefit is related to the decreasing cost of borrowing. This type securitization is very attractive for investors due to its flawless

performance and few recorded failures. In addition, many risks are mitigated and the securities are bought by large number of various investors thus reducing the spread. Like the BdB securitization deal, Lebanon has a potential to save over 700 basis points. Thus, though the RBSs and the higher rating the cost of borrowing will significantly decrease.

Extension of maturities. Another benefit of getting engaged with RBSs is extended maturities. The investment grade of remittance-backed securities enables larger specter of investors to buy such a security. Such investors as pension or mutual fund are allowed to invest only in investment grade securities. In addition, these types of investors tend to hold their securities until the maturity. This benefit is particularly important for Lebanon since one of the goals of the debt management strategy is longer maturities of the public debt.

External benefits. In addition to mentioned above, Lebanon will benefit from several externalities. Once Lebanon will decide to issue RBSs, advisers from IMF and WB would assist the local authorities in the improving legal framework in ways so the transactions may take place. Also, in order to secure the securitization transaction, Lebanon would have to establish close relationship with its diaspora in order to increase amount of remittances inflows. In addition, in order to encourage official remittances transfers, banks may be willing decrease the cost per such transfer.

Obstacles of remittance-backed securities. In addition to obviously attractive benefits there are several obstacles that prevent many developing countries from creation of the RBSs. First of all, creation of such securities is expensive. Fixed costs per transaction are often around US\$2 million (which includes credit rating fees) (Suhas & Ratha, 2002). Also, preparation of the deal is time consuming. In addition, in most of the cases IMF and WB may require the improvement of the legal

framework (particularly, creation of bankruptcy law). This may include inaction of several laws that may take some time taking into consideration the current political situation in Lebanon.

CHAPTER 5

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The final chapter of this work will present the results of the research through the summary of the finding in the field work. In addition, the conclusions and recommendations will be drawn. Since the main goal of this research is to highlight the possibility of the public debt financing through remittance-backed securities, the following hypotheses have been tested:

- H₁: There is a need for Lebanon to obtain financing from international markets.
- H₂: There is a way to get financing through remittance-backed securities.
- H₃: There is a potential borrowing method from international markets using remittances inflows to Lebanon.
- H₄: There are benefits for Lebanon from borrowing throughout remittance-backed securities.

The following part provides a summary of the research and the results of hypotheses testing.

Summary of Findings

Public Debt

As the study revealed, the public debt is a severe burden to the Lebanese economy. Due to several reasons, the Lebanese public debt constantly increases. Authorities asked for external help only twice addressing the French president Chirac and acquiring necessary fund for the maturity swap of the debt through the Paris Club, in 2002 and 2007. Until now the largest portion of the debt has been held by the

Lebanese citizens. The smaller portion of the total debt, below 10%, belongs to non-residents who provided help in terms of the Paris conference and the Council of Development and Reconstruction.

As performed data analysis in terms of time series and multiple regression revealed, the local public debt is at its increasing trend. In addition, net public debt has a positive correlation with the GDP implying that the debt will continue growing with the growth of GDP.

Several suggestions of the government and of the S&P's credit rating agency are the following. The Ministry of Finance of Lebanon established the medium-term goal to increase borrowing in foreign currency at a lowest possible cost. Both MOF and credit rating agencies have concerns about the amount of the public debt and the limited absorption capacity of the Lebanese market. MOF considers the current situation of the growing public debt and limited absorption as a potential "bottle neck". In addition, S&P's sees the current public debt situation as a factor that adds vulnerability of business, economic and financial situation of Lebanon.

Although it is not directly stated by the local government authorities, all of the mentioned above proved the first hypothesis: **H₁: There is a need to get financing from international market.**

Development Financing

Recently, many researchers suggest several innovative techniques to developing countries that lack access to international markets. Since most of the developing countries experience migration outflows to developed countries, the countries of origin most of the time experience inflows of sent back home money, remittances. IMF and the World Bank advise leveraging those remittances and obtaining funds necessary for development through remittance-backed securities. Here

there is an example of the obtaining required financing through remittance-backed securities. The second hypothesis: **H₂: There is a way to get financing through remittance-backed securities** is tested positively.

Remittances

Being a constantly migrating country, Lebanon faces an outflow of educated and skilled workers. Despite the fact that the local economy loses its workers, the country benefits from the financial inflows that expatriates send back to the country of origin. These remittance inflows into Lebanon not only benefit the receiving family, but also support the receiving country in terms of improvement of current account of balance of payment. In addition, remittances are sent in hard currency thus increasing foreign exchange reserves.

According to the time series analysis, linear trend and forecasts of the data retrieved from the Central Bank of Lebanon, net remittances in Lebanon historically have an increasing trend. They are always positive and even countercyclical. In addition, as forecasts revealed in the near future remittances will remain at nearly the same level as in 2013 and 2014 without significant decrease.

Lebanon is one of the major remittance-receiving countries in the world; however, the substantial amount of remittances does not correlate with economic development and growth. Lebanese authorities do not leverage remittances despite the obvious possibility of doing so.

Remittance-backed securities are securities that are issued by government or private entities and backed by the constant inflow of funds that are sent by migrants back to their home country. Being mostly used by developing countries, RBS is recently new financial innovations that allows speculative sovereign access international market and borrow at a lower interest rate. Being very popular during

1990s, RBSs allowed many developing countries, such as Mexico, El Salvador, Brazil, Russia and Turkey to borrow internationally during time of liquidity crises. Relying on this information, the third hypothesis is tested positively: **H₃: There is borrowing method from international markets using remittance inflows to Lebanon.** Thus, Lebanon has a potential to borrow internationally engaging remittances inflow.

Remittance-backed Securities Benefits

Finally, the last hypothesis: **H₄: There are benefits for Lebanon from borrowing throughout remittance-backed securities** - have been tested.

Due to the nature of the structure of RBSs that takes place offshore, Lebanon has the potential to benefit in several ways, such as international market access, lower cost of debt, extension of maturities and externalities. Being a country with a speculative credit rating, Lebanon is not able to borrow internationally at an acceptable interest rate. Remittances provide this opportunity. Borrowing from international markets through remittances lifts the sovereign rating ceiling up to 5 notches providing acceptable rating of the deal thus tolerable interest rate. Thus, Lebanon will be able to access international markets at a lower interest rate. Another important benefit is extension of maturities. Being one of the goals of the Debt Management strategy of Lebanon, extension of maturities takes place due to the nature of remittance-backed securities and international investors. RBSs usually have medium to long term maturity, while investors tend to buy those securities and hold them until they mature. Finally, if engaged in securitization, Lebanon has a potential to benefit from externalities that usually take place during preparation to securitization process. Such externalities may be improvement of legal infrastructure

of Lebanon, establishment of closer relationship with diaspora, and even decreased cost of remittance transfers.

Conclusion

The major conclusions of our research are the following:

1. Public debt is the severe burden of the Lebanese economy. Lebanon has one of the highest in the world total debt-to-GDP ratios which was nearly 140% and net total debt-to-GDP ratio of nearly 120% in 2015. Most of the local debt is held by the Lebanese while only less than 10 percent held by foreign parties. Constantly increasing debt due to twin deficit (current account and budget deficits) and limited absorption capacity of the local market put the Lebanese economy at risk.

2. Lebanon has constant migration and its diaspora surpasses the total number of people that live in Lebanon. Despite the constant loss of skilled workers, migration by Lebanese benefits the country in many ways. First, money that is sent back home by migrants benefits the receiving families. Second, remittances benefit local communities if they are sent for development purposes. Finally, remittances improve Lebanon's balance of payment while providing hard currency inflow that is important for a country with a fixed exchange rate. Nevertheless, inflow of remittances has no correlation with growth meaning that the Lebanese government underutilizes the whole specter of benefits that remittances provide.

3. Securitization of remittances is relatively recent financial instrument that allows developing country to lift their credit rating ceiling and attempt to borrow from the international market. Many developing countries, like Brazil and El-Salvador, issued remittance-backed securities and were able to raise substantial amounts of money for the development. Having a large and countercyclical amount of remittance

inflows, Lebanon is potentially able to use securitization particularly in form of remittance-backed securities for international borrowing.

Combining those three major conclusions we have reached the main one: Lebanon is capable of leveraging the effect of remittances for raising external financing for the public debt through remittance-backed securities.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the presented work the following recommendations are proposed. First, I believe that the Lebanese government should consider international borrowing due to the increasing amount of the public debt and limited capability of the local market in funding this debt.

Second, Lebanon should leverage expatriates' remittances for the common good of the country. Thus, I suggest that Lebanon should redress the economy, using those remittance inflows to improve the current public debt situation beyond relying on remittances' contribution to the current account. Based on the research it could be done through international borrowing using RBSs. Since they allow access to international markets while decreasing the cost of financing, Lebanese authorities should consider this innovative instrument as the public debt management technique. This would provide additional funds at a lower interest rate while allowing borrowing in foreign currencies and from international markets. Also, it will partially free the local commercial banks from the burden of obligatory holding of the public treasury.

Finally, if the government would decide to do so, the next step is to stimulate and attempt to increase remittance inflows to Lebanon. There are several ways how Lebanon can do so. According to the Global Economic Prospects (2006), remittances could be encouraged through the following instruments:

1. Establishing home town associations (HTAs). Establishment of an institutional agreement to support diaspora welfare abroad will encourage home-diaspora relationships.
2. Encouraging domestic banks to operate overseas in order to provide services for emigrants by
 - a) Creating ID cards for migrants so they could access banking facilities
 - b) Creating loans/pension schemes and bond that target diasporas

Figure 41 summarizes the rationale of the study, the conclusion and recommendations described in this chapter.

Figure 41. Rationale, conclusion and recommendation of the study.

Self-made figure based on the knowledge of chapters 2, 4 and 5.

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APPENDIX A
QUALITATIVE DATA

Balance of Payment Components

A. Current Account

A.1 – Goods

A.2 – Services

A.2-1. Transportation

A.2-2. Travel

A.2-3. Other Services

- Insurance
- Other Services

A.3. – Income

A.3-1. Compensation of Employees

A.3-2. Investment Income

- Direct Investment
- Portfolio Investment
- Other Investment

A.4. – Current Transfers

A.4-1. General Government

A.4-2. Other Sectors

- Workers' Remittances
- Other Transfers

B. Capital and Financial Account

B.1 – Capital Account

B.2 – Financial Account

B.2-1. Direct Investment

B.2-2. Portfolio Investment

- Equity
- Debt

B.2-3. Other Investment

B.2-4. Reserve Assets

C. Net Errors and Omissions

Source: Balance of Payment Methodology, BDL, 2013

Fiscal Balance of Lebanon

I. Total Revenue

1. Tax Revenue
 - a. *Taxes on Income, Profits, & Capital Gains*
 - b. *Taxes on Properties*
 - c. *Domestic Taxes of Goods and Services*
 - d. *Taxes of International Trade*
 - e. *Other Tax Revenues (namely fiscal stamp fees)*
2. Non-Tax Revenue
 - a. *Income from Public Institutions and Government Properties*
 - b. *Administrative Fees and Charges*
 - c. *Penalties and Confiscations*
 - d. *Other Non-Tax Revenues (mostly retirement deductibles)*
3. Treasury Receipts

II. Total Expenditures

1. Current Expenditures
 - a. *Personnel Cost*
 - b. *Interest Payments (domestic and foreign interest payments)*
 - c. *Foreign Debt Principal Repayment*
 - d. *Materials and Supplies*
 - e. *External Services*
 - f. *Various Transfers*
 - g. *Other Current*
 - h. *Reserves*
2. Capital Expenditures
 - a. *Acquisitions of Land, Buildings, for the Construction of Roads, Ports, Airports, and Water Networks*
 - b. *Equipment*
 - c. *Construction in Progress*
 - d. *Maintenance*
 - e. *Other Expenditures Related to Fixed Capital Assets*
 - f. *Parliamentary Equipment and Maintenance*
3. Budget Advances
4. Custom Administration (excl. Salaries and Wages)
5. Other Treasury Expenditures
 - a. *Municipalities*
 - b. *Guarantees*
 - c. *Deposits*
 - d. *Other*
 - e. *Treasury Advances for Water Authorities*
6. Unclassified Expenditures

III. Gross Public Debt

1. Local Currency Debt
2. Currency Debt

Source: Ministry of Finance, 2011

APPENDIX B
QUANTITATIVE DATA

Fiscal Performance of the Lebanese Economy (1992-2010)

(in LL billion)	Total Revenue	Tax Revenue	Non Tax Revenue	Treasury Revenue	Total Expenditures	Wages and Salaries	Interest Payments and Foreign Debt Principal Repayment	Other Current Expenditures	Capital Expenditures	Other Treasury Expenditures, Unclassified Expenditures and Customs Cashiers
2010	12,684	9,976	2,043	666	17,047	5,056	6,218	1,648	691	3434
2009	12,705	8,967	3,069	669	17,167	4,936	6,087	1,594	550	4000
2008	10,553	7,182	2,613	758	14,957	3,970	5,304	1,364	514	3804
2007	8,749	5,583	2,511	655	12,587	3,583	4,940	1,138	558	2367
2006	7,316	4,943	1,945	428	11,879	3,307	4,557	1,063	551	2401
2005	7,405	4,867	2,117	421	10,203	3,193	3,534	1,197	534	1,745
2004	7,515	5,169	1,907	439	10,541	3,094	4,021	937	817	1,672
2003	6,655	4,502	1,717	436	10,593	3,087	4,874	871	714	1,047
2002	5,830	3,995	1,390	445	10,139	3,008	4,622	691	610	1,208
2001	4,646	2,961	1,299	386	8,875	2,992	4,312	626	325	620
2000	4,684	2,934	1,238	512	10,621	2,908	4,197	863	900	1,754
1999	4,873	3,350	1,109	414	8,453	2,760	3,624	709	1,097	265
1998	4,449	3,097	882	470	7,906	2,352	3,352	798	1,061	343
1997	4,010	2,684	579	747	9,162	2,466	3,378	1,851	1,467	n.a
1996	3,534	2,869	665	n.a	7,225	2,261	2,653	1,088	1,223	n.a
1995	3,033	2,100	933	n.a	5,856	1,869	1,875	896	1,216	n.a
1994	2,241	1,656	585	n.a	5,204	1,710	1,488	756	1,250	n.a
1993	1,855	1,208	647	n.a	3,017	1,295	784	545	393	n.a
1992	1,138	n.a	n.a	n.a	2,219	660	518	895	146	n.a

Source: Banque du Liban (BDL)

Outstanding public debt by type of holder, end of period, billion LBP

Year And Month	Total Debt	Local Currency Debt				Foreign Currency Debt					
		Central				IDI**	FG+	Paris II		Total	
		Bank	Banks	Others ⁽¹⁾	Total			loans	Others ⁽²⁾		
2013	Dec	95,710	17,171	29,905	9,236	56,312	1,871	1,556	208	35,763	39,398
2014	Apr	97,799	17,639	30,518	10,239	58,396	1,830	1,838	167	35,568	39,403
	May	98,126	17,745	30,479	10,328	58,552	1,800	1,933	164	35,677	39,574
	Jun	99,082	17,851	31,514	10,371	59,736	1,747	1,946	164	35,489	39,346
	Jul	98,958	18,011	31,209	10,409	59,629	1,716	1,960	161	35,492	39,329
	Aug	99,319	18,397	31,186	10,336	59,919	1,693	1,937	139	35,631	39,400
	Sep	99,495	18,804	31,170	10,300	60,274	1,660	1,883	133	35,545	39,221
	Oct	99,849	19,250	30,981	10,468	60,699	1,651	1,869	133	35,497	39,150
	Nov	100,453	19,705	31,410	10,498	61,613	1,624	1,859	131	35,226	38,840
	Dec	100,363	19,855	31,468	10,429	61,752	1,619	1,839	128	35,025	38,611
2015	Jan	100,374	20,363	31,366	10,505	62,234	1,584	1,800	119	34,637	38,140
	Feb	104,390	20,572	31,674	10,584	62,830	1,571	1,792	101	38,096	41,560
	Mar	104,675	21,607	31,116	10,537	63,260	1,545	1,745	97	38,028	41,415
	Apr	104,708	21,769	30,913	10,648	63,330	1,538	1,747	101	37,992	41,378

Source :BDL.

* The figures are equal to the principal paid plus the interests due.

** IDI : International Development Institutions.

+ FG : Foreign Governments.

(1) Include: public TB's, public entities TB's and financial institutions TB's.

(2) Include: Eurobonds holders (banks, non banks, residents and non residents), foreign private sector loans and special TB's in FC (expropriation bonds).

<http://www.abl.org.lb/Library/Files/Files/Economic%20Letter%20April%202015.pdf>

Net remittances (2002-2016),
million USD

Year	Net Remittances. Million USD
Y2002	34.7
Y2003	270.0
Y2004	1609.5
Y2005	976.3
Y2006	1839.1
Y2007	2657.6
Y2008	2198.8
Y2009	1669.7
Y2010	2491.2
Y2011	2463.1
Y2012	2063.1
Y2013	2322.1
Y2014	2809.4
Y2015	3577.5
Y2016	1496.5

Source: www.bdl.gov.lb

Public Debt. Net total debt.GDP. Debt-to-GDP, December						
Year	Billion LBP	USD Public Debt.	Billion USD	Public Debt Growth	GDP	Debt-to-GDP
Y1993	4,974	1507.5	3.3	-	7.5	44
Y1994	7,983	1507.5	5.3	61	9.6	55
Y1995	11,431	1507.5	7.6	43	11.7	65
Y1996	16,319	1507.5	10.8	42.8	13.7	79
Y1997	22,095	1507.5	14.7	35.4	15.6	94
Y1998	25,842	1507.5	17.1	17.0	17.2	99.7
Y1999	29,712	1507.5	19.7	15.0	17.4	113
Y2000	35,358	1507.5	23.5	19.0	17.3	136
Y2001	40,731	1507.5	27.0	15.2	17.6	154
Y2002	44,312	1507.5	29.4	8.8	19.2	153
Y2003	47,280	1507.5	31.4	6.7	20.1	156
Y2004	49,723	1507.5	33.0	5.2	21	157
Y2005	52,395	1507.5	34.8	5.4	21.3	163
Y2006	56,413	1507.5	37.4	7.7	21.8	172
Y2007	58,837	1507.5	39.0	4.3	24.6	159
Y2008	62,615	1507.5	41.5	6.4	28.8	144
Y2009	66,590	1507.5	44.2	6.3	35.1	126
Y2010	67,879	1507.5	45.0	1.9	38.0	118
Y2011	69,903	1507.5	46.4	3.0	40.1	116
Y2012	74,043	1507.5	49.1	5.9	43.2	114
Y2013	80,215	1507.5	53.2	8.3	44.4	120
Y2014	86,391	1507.5	57.3	7.7	45.7	125
Y2015	92,784	1507.5	61.5	7.4	51.2	120

Source: www.bdl.gov.lb

CURRICULUM VITAE

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Personal Information

Date of birth:	November 19, 1985
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Civil status:	Married
Citizenship:	Belarussian
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Educational Background

2012 – 2017	MBA Finance, Middle East University, Magna cum Laude
2016 – 2017	Social Media Marketing, Webcom Academy, Belarus
2009 – 2012	BA Finance and Banking, Middle East University, Magna cum Laude, GPA – 3.8

Work Experience

2017 – present	In-country Analyst for Belarus, Euromonitor International
2015 – 2016	Part-time Economics and Business Teacher, Cedars High School, Lebanon
2012 – 2016	Assistant Business Manager, Middle East University, Lebanon